

Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*During past years, author worked with magic squares in different situations. These are of **digital-type, block-wise, block-bordered, bordered, creative-type, 2-digits, magic-crosses, magic letters and magic numbers**, etc. The detailed study can be seen in the reference list. The magic square summing 2020, 2021 etc. are also studied with different properties [22, 23, 27]. In this work, **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic squares are constructed in such a way that the final magic sum in each case is always 2022. The work is for the orders 3 to 22. The entries are either **fractional, decimal and whole numbers** with positive and/or negative values.*

Contents

1 Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7	1
1.1 Magic Square of Order 3	1
1.2 Magic Square of Order 4	2
1.3 Magic Square of Order 5	2
1.4 Magic Square of Order 6	2
1.5 Magic Square of Order 7	3
2 Block-Wise and Bordered Magic Squares	3
2.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 8	3
2.2 Block-Wise Magic Square of Order 9	4
2.3 Bordered Magic Square of Order 10	5
2.4 Bordered Magic Square of Order 11	5
2.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12	6

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <https://inderjtaneja.com>; <https://indertaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

2.5.1	Block Of Order 3	6
2.5.2	Block Of Order 4	7
2.5.3	Block Of Order 6	8
2.6	Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 13	9
2.7	Block-Boarded Magic Square of Order 14	10
2.7.1	Block Of Order 3	10
2.7.2	Block Of Order 4	11
2.7.3	Block Of Order 6	12
2.8	Bordered Magic Square of Order 15	13
2.8.1	Blocks of Order 3	13
2.8.2	Blocks of Order 5	14
2.9	Block-Wise and Block-Bordred Magic Squares of Order 16	15
2.9.1	Block-Wise	15
2.9.2	Block-Bordered	16
2.10	Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 17	17
2.10.1	Blocks of Order 3	17
2.10.2	Blocks of Order 5	18
2.11	Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 18	19
2.11.1	Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 3	19
2.11.2	Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 6	20
2.11.3	Block-Bordered With Blocks of Order 4	21
2.11.4	Block-Bordered With Blocks of Order 8	22
2.12	Bordered Magic Square of Order 19	23
2.12.1	Blocks of Order 3	23
2.12.2	Blocks of Order 5	24
2.13	Block-Wise and Blokc-Bordered Magic Square of Order 20	25
2.13.1	Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 4	25
2.13.2	Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 5	26
2.13.3	Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10	27
2.13.4	Bordered Magic Squares Of Order 10	28
2.14	Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 21	29
2.14.1	Blocks of Order 3	29
2.14.2	Blocks of Order 7	30
2.15	Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 22	31
2.15.1	Blocks of Order 4	31

2.15.2 Blocks of Order 5 32

1 Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7

Below are magic squares of orders 3 to 7 with magic sum 2022. The magic squares of orders 4, 5 and 7 are **pandiagonal**.

1.1 Magic Square of Order 3

A **magic square** of order 3 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

			2022
673	678	671	2022
672	674	676	2022
677	670	675	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022

1.2 Magic Square of Order 4

A **magic square** of order 4 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022
	504	509	498	511	2022
2022	499	510	505	508	2022
2022	513	500	507	502	2022
2022	506	503	512	501	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the magic square is **pandiagonal**.

1.3 Magic Square of Order 5

A **magic square** of order 5 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
	392,4	398,4	404,4	410,4	416,4	2022
2022	409,4	415,4	396,4	397,4	403,4	2022
2022	401,4	402,4	408,4	414,4	395,4	2022
2022	413,4	394,4	400,4	406,4	407,4	2022
2022	405,4	411,4	412,4	393,4	399,4	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the magic square is **pandiagonal**.

1.4 Magic Square of Order 6

A **magic square** of order 6 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

						2022
319,5	341,5	346,5	352,5	335,5	326,5	2022
347,5	325,5	353,5	332,5	339,5	323,5	2022
330,5	324,5	331,5	345,5	349,5	340,5	2022
350,5	334,5	322,5	342,5	328,5	343,5	2022
337,5	351,5	329,5	321,5	348,5	333,5	2022
336,5	344,5	338,5	327,5	320,5	354,5	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

1.5 Magic Square of Order 7

A **magic square** of order 7 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	264 6/7	272 6/7	280 6/7	288 6/7	296 6/7	304 6/7	312 6/7	2022	
2022	303 6/7	311 6/7	270 6/7	271 6/7	279 6/7	287 6/7	295 6/7	2022	
2022	286 6/7	294 6/7	302 6/7	310 6/7	269 6/7	277 6/7	278 6/7	2022	
2022	276 6/7	284 6/7	285 6/7	293 6/7	301 6/7	309 6/7	268 6/7	2022	
2022	308 6/7	267 6/7	275 6/7	283 6/7	291 6/7	292 6/7	300 6/7	2022	
2022	298 6/7	299 6/7	307 6/7	266 6/7	274 6/7	282 6/7	290 6/7	2022	
	281 6/7	289 6/7	297 6/7	305 6/7	306 6/7	265 6/7	273 6/7	2022	
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	

2 Block-Wise and Bordered Magic Squares

Below are magic squares of order 8 to 22 with magic sum 2022. These magic squares are written **block-wise** and **block-bordered** way.

2.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 8

A **block-wise** magic square of order 8 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	249,25	260,25	221,25	280,25	241,25	268,25	229,25	272,25	2022
2022	224,25	277,25	252,25	257,25	232,25	269,25	244,25	265,25	2022
2022	284,25	225,25	256,25	245,25	276,25	233,25	264,25	237,25	2022
2022	253,25	248,25	281,25	228,25	261,25	240,25	273,25	236,25	2022
2022	250,25	259,25	222,25	279,25	242,25	267,25	230,25	271,25	2022
2022	223,25	278,25	251,25	258,25	231,25	270,25	243,25	266,25	2022
2022	283,25	226,25	255,25	246,25	275,25	234,25	263,25	238,25	2022
	254,25	247,25	282,25	227,25	262,25	239,25	274,25	235,25	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **pandigonal** magic square with blocks of equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{8 \times 8} := 2022$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 1011$

2.2 Block-Wise Magic Square of Order 9

A **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	205 2/3	254 2/3	213 2/3	210 2/3	247 2/3	215 2/3	203 2/3	252 2/3	217 2/3	2022
2022	218 2/3	204 2/3	250 2/3	211 2/3	206 2/3	255 2/3	216 2/3	208 2/3	248 2/3	2022
2022	249 2/3	214 2/3	209 2/3	251 2/3	219 2/3	202 2/3	253 2/3	212 2/3	207 2/3	2022
2022	223 2/3	191 2/3	258 2/3	228 2/3	184 2/3	260 2/3	221 2/3	189 2/3	262 2/3	2022
2022	263 2/3	222 2/3	187 2/3	256 2/3	224 2/3	192 2/3	261 2/3	226 2/3	185 2/3	2022
2022	186 2/3	259 2/3	227 2/3	188 2/3	264 2/3	220 2/3	190 2/3	257 2/3	225 2/3	2022
2022	241 2/3	236 2/3	195 2/3	246 2/3	229 2/3	197 2/3	239 2/3	234 2/3	199 2/3	2022
2022	200 2/3	240 2/3	232 2/3	193 2/3	242 2/3	237 2/3	198 2/3	244 2/3	230 2/3	2022
	231 2/3	196 2/3	245 2/3	233 2/3	201 2/3	238 2/3	235 2/3	194 2/3	243 2/3	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **pandigonal** magic square with blocks of equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. In this case the **magic** and **semi-magic** sums are $S_{9 \times 9} := 2022$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{2022}{3} := 674$

2.3 Bordered Magic Square of Order 10

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

										2022
242,7	237,7	167,7	235,7	169,7	165,7	155,7	249,7	153,7	243,7	2022
164,7	198,7	209,7	170,7	229,7	190,7	217,7	178,7	221,7	239,7	2022
240,7	173,7	226,7	201,7	206,7	181,7	218,7	193,7	214,7	163,7	2022
162,7	233,7	174,7	205,7	194,7	225,7	182,7	213,7	186,7	241,7	2022
247,7	202,7	197,7	230,7	177,7	210,7	189,7	222,7	185,7	156,7	2022
152,7	199,7	208,7	171,7	228,7	191,7	216,7	179,7	220,7	251,7	2022
244,7	172,7	227,7	200,7	207,7	180,7	219,7	192,7	215,7	159,7	2022
158,7	232,7	175,7	204,7	195,7	224,7	183,7	212,7	187,7	245,7	2022
246,7	203,7	196,7	231,7	176,7	211,7	188,7	223,7	184,7	157,7	2022
160,7	166,7	236,7	168,7	234,7	238,7	248,7	154,7	250,7	161,7	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **block-bordered** magic square with inner block a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 composed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{10 \times 10} := 2022$, $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8088}{5} = 1617.6$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4044}{5} = 808.8$.

2.4 Bordered Magic Square of Order 11

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

											2022
134 9/11	142 9/11	140 9/11	138 9/11	136 9/11	235 9/11	236 9/11	238 9/11	240 9/11	242 9/11	132 9/11	2022
243 9/11	164 9/11	213 9/11	172 9/11	169 9/11	206 9/11	174 9/11	162 9/11	211 9/11	176 9/11	123 9/11	2022
241 9/11	177 9/11	163 9/11	209 9/11	170 9/11	165 9/11	214 9/11	175 9/11	167 9/11	207 9/11	125 9/11	2022
239 9/11	208 9/11	173 9/11	168 9/11	210 9/11	178 9/11	161 9/11	212 9/11	171 9/11	166 9/11	127 9/11	2022
237 9/11	182 9/11	150 9/11	217 9/11	187 9/11	143 9/11	219 9/11	180 9/11	148 9/11	221 9/11	129 9/11	2022
133 9/11	222 9/11	181 9/11	146 9/11	215 9/11	183 9/11	151 9/11	220 9/11	185 9/11	144 9/11	233 9/11	2022
135 9/11	145 9/11	218 9/11	186 9/11	147 9/11	223 9/11	179 9/11	149 9/11	216 9/11	184 9/11	231 9/11	2022
137 9/11	200 9/11	195 9/11	154 9/11	205 9/11	188 9/11	156 9/11	198 9/11	193 9/11	158 9/11	229 9/11	2022
139 9/11	159 9/11	199 9/11	191 9/11	152 9/11	201 9/11	196 9/11	157 9/11	203 9/11	189 9/11	227 9/11	2022
141 9/11	190 9/11	155 9/11	204 9/11	192 9/11	160 9/11	197 9/11	194 9/11	153 9/11	202 9/11	225 9/11	2022
234 9/11	224 9/11	226 9/11	228 9/11	230 9/11	131 9/11	130 9/11	128 9/11	126 9/11	124 9/11	232 9/11	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **block-bordered** magic square with inner block a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 composed by 9 equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. In this case the magic sums are $S_{11 \times 11} := 2022$, $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18198}{11}$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{6066}{11}$.

2.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are **block-wise** magic squares of order 12 with blocks of orders 3, 4 and 5.

2.5.1 Block Of Order 3

A **block-wise** magic square of order 12 with blocks of order 3 with magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	194	97	147	168	118	215	174	124	221	236	139	189	2022
2022	99	146	193	214	167	120	220	173	126	141	188	235	2022
2022	145	195	98	119	216	166	125	222	172	187	237	140	2022
2022	227	130	180	183	133	230	153	103	200	209	112	162	2022
2022	132	179	226	229	182	135	199	152	105	114	161	208	2022
2022	178	228	131	134	231	181	104	201	151	160	210	113	2022
2022	163	213	116	101	198	148	143	240	190	169	219	122	2022
2022	117	164	211	196	149	102	238	191	144	123	170	217	2022
2022	212	115	165	150	100	197	192	142	239	218	121	171	2022
2022	184	234	137	128	225	175	110	207	157	154	204	107	2022
2022	138	185	232	223	176	129	205	158	111	108	155	202	2022
	233	136	186	177	127	224	159	109	206	203	106	156	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **pandigonal** magic square of order 12 with different magic sums of order 3.

2.5.2 Block Of Order 4

A **block-wise** magic square of order 12 with blocks of order 4 with magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	151	204	97	222	152	203	98	221	153	202	99	220	2022
2022	114	205	168	187	113	206	167	188	112	207	166	189	2022
2022	240	115	186	133	239	116	185	134	238	117	184	135	2022
2022	169	150	223	132	170	149	224	131	171	148	225	130	2022
2022	154	201	100	219	155	200	101	218	156	199	102	217	2022
2022	111	208	165	190	110	209	164	191	109	210	163	192	2022
2022	237	118	183	136	236	119	182	137	235	120	181	138	2022
2022	172	147	226	129	173	146	227	128	174	145	228	127	2022
2022	157	198	103	216	158	197	104	215	159	196	105	214	2022
2022	108	211	162	193	107	212	161	194	106	213	160	195	2022
2022	234	121	180	139	233	122	179	140	232	123	178	141	2022
	175	144	229	126	176	143	230	125	177	142	231	124	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **pandigonal** magic square of order 12 with equal sums **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{12 \times 12} := 2022$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 674$.

2.5.3 Block Of Order 6

A **block-wise** magic square of order 12 with blocks of order 6 with magic sum 2022 is given by

												2022
97	233	232	225	104	120	98	234	231	226	103	119	2022
216	128	208	129	137	193	215	127	207	130	138	194	2022
192	185	153	160	176	145	191	186	154	159	175	146	2022
168	152	177	184	161	169	167	151	178	183	162	170	2022
121	200	136	201	209	144	122	199	135	202	210	143	2022
217	113	105	112	224	240	218	114	106	111	223	239	2022
99	235	230	227	102	118	100	236	229	228	101	117	2022
214	126	206	131	139	195	213	125	205	132	140	196	2022
190	187	155	158	174	147	189	188	156	157	173	148	2022
166	150	179	182	163	171	165	149	180	181	164	172	2022
123	198	134	203	211	142	124	197	133	204	212	141	2022
219	115	107	110	222	238	220	116	108	109	221	237	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is magic square of order 12 with equal sums magic square of order 6. In this case the magic sums are $S_{12 \times 12} := 2022$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 1011$.

2.6 Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 13

A **block-bordered** of order 13 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

													2022
226 7/13	217 7/13	219 7/13	221 7/13	223 7/13	225 7/13	227 7/13	79 7/13	77 7/13	75 7/13	73 7/13	71 7/13	82 7/13	2022
72 7/13	106 7/13	114 7/13	112 7/13	110 7/13	108 7/13	207 7/13	208 7/13	210 7/13	212 7/13	214 7/13	104 7/13	238 7/13	2022
74 7/13	215 7/13	136 7/13	185 7/13	144 7/13	141 7/13	178 7/13	146 7/13	134 7/13	183 7/13	148 7/13	95 7/13	236 7/13	2022
76 7/13	213 7/13	149 7/13	135 7/13	181 7/13	142 7/13	137 7/13	186 7/13	147 7/13	139 7/13	179 7/13	97 7/13	234 7/13	2022
78 7/13	211 7/13	180 7/13	145 7/13	140 7/13	182 7/13	150 7/13	133 7/13	184 7/13	143 7/13	138 7/13	99 7/13	232 7/13	2022
80 7/13	209 7/13	154 7/13	122 7/13	189 7/13	159 7/13	115 7/13	191 7/13	152 7/13	120 7/13	193 7/13	101 7/13	230 7/13	2022
81 7/13	105 7/13	194 7/13	153 7/13	118 7/13	187 7/13	155 7/13	123 7/13	192 7/13	157 7/13	116 7/13	205 7/13	229 7/13	2022
224 7/13	107 7/13	117 7/13	190 7/13	158 7/13	119 7/13	195 7/13	151 7/13	121 7/13	188 7/13	156 7/13	203 7/13	86 7/13	2022
222 7/13	109 7/13	172 7/13	167 7/13	126 7/13	177 7/13	160 7/13	128 7/13	170 7/13	165 7/13	130 7/13	201 7/13	88 7/13	2022
220 7/13	111 7/13	131 7/13	171 7/13	163 7/13	124 7/13	173 7/13	168 7/13	129 7/13	175 7/13	161 7/13	199 7/13	90 7/13	2022
218 7/13	113 7/13	162 7/13	127 7/13	176 7/13	164 7/13	132 7/13	169 7/13	166 7/13	125 7/13	174 7/13	197 7/13	92 7/13	2022
216 7/13	206 7/13	196 7/13	198 7/13	200 7/13	202 7/13	103 7/13	102 7/13	100 7/13	98 7/13	96 7/13	204 7/13	94 7/13	2022
228 7/13	93 7/13	91 7/13	89 7/13	87 7/13	85 7/13	83 7/13	231 7/13	233 7/13	235 7/13	237 7/13	239 7/13	84 7/13	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

It is **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 with inner block a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 composed by 9 equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. In this case the magic sums are $S_{13 \times 13} := 2022$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{22242}{13}$, $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{18198}{13}$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{6066}{13}$.

2.7 Block-Boarded Magic Square of Order 14

In this case, we shall write, three types of **block-boarded** magic square of order 14 with magic sum 2022. For the inner block of order 12, the blocks of orders 3, 4 and 6 are considered.

2.7.1 Block Of Order 3

A **block bordered** magic square of order 14 with inner magic square of order 12 composed by blocks of order 3 with magic sum 2022 is given by

														2022
59 13/14	53 13/14	233 13/14	55 13/14	231 13/14	57 13/14	241 13/14	52 13/14	227 13/14	61 13/14	225 13/14	63 13/14	223 13/14	229 13/14	2022
240 13/14	169 13/14	72 13/14	122 13/14	143 13/14	93 13/14	190 13/14	149 13/14	99 13/14	196 13/14	211 13/14	114 13/14	164 13/14	47 13/14	2022
48 13/14	74 13/14	121 13/14	168 13/14	189 13/14	142 13/14	95 13/14	195 13/14	148 13/14	101 13/14	116 13/14	163 13/14	210 13/14	239 13/14	2022
238 13/14	120 13/14	170 13/14	73 13/14	94 13/14	191 13/14	141 13/14	100 13/14	197 13/14	147 13/14	162 13/14	212 13/14	115 13/14	49 13/14	2022
50 13/14	202 13/14	105 13/14	155 13/14	158 13/14	108 13/14	205 13/14	128 13/14	78 13/14	175 13/14	184 13/14	87 13/14	137 13/14	237 13/14	2022
236 13/14	107 13/14	154 13/14	201 13/14	204 13/14	157 13/14	110 13/14	174 13/14	127 13/14	80 13/14	89 13/14	136 13/14	183 13/14	51 13/14	2022
222 13/14	153 13/14	203 13/14	106 13/14	109 13/14	206 13/14	156 13/14	79 13/14	176 13/14	126 13/14	135 13/14	185 13/14	88 13/14	65 13/14	2022
216 13/14	138 13/14	188 13/14	91 13/14	76 13/14	173 13/14	123 13/14	118 13/14	215 13/14	165 13/14	144 13/14	194 13/14	97 13/14	71 13/14	2022
70 13/14	92 13/14	139 13/14	186 13/14	171 13/14	124 13/14	77 13/14	213 13/14	166 13/14	119 13/14	98 13/14	145 13/14	192 13/14	217 13/14	2022
218 13/14	187 13/14	90 13/14	140 13/14	125 13/14	75 13/14	172 13/14	167 13/14	117 13/14	214 13/14	193 13/14	96 13/14	146 13/14	69 13/14	2022
68 13/14	159 13/14	209 13/14	112 13/14	103 13/14	200 13/14	150 13/14	85 13/14	182 13/14	132 13/14	129 13/14	179 13/14	82 13/14	219 13/14	2022
220 13/14	113 13/14	160 13/14	207 13/14	198 13/14	151 13/14	104 13/14	180 13/14	133 13/14	86 13/14	83 13/14	130 13/14	177 13/14	67 13/14	2022
66 13/14	208 13/14	111 13/14	161 13/14	152 13/14	102 13/14	199 13/14	134 13/14	84 13/14	181 13/14	178 13/14	81 13/14	131 13/14	221 13/14	2022
58 13/14	234 13/14	54 13/14	232 13/14	56 13/14	230 13/14	46 13/14	235 13/14	60 13/14	226 13/14	62 13/14	224 13/14	64 13/14	228 13/14	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the inner block of order 12 is a **pandigonal** magic square of order 12 with different magic sums of order 3.

2.7.2 Block Of Order 4

A **block bordered** magic square of order 14 with inner magic square of order 12 composed by blocks of order 4 with magic sum 2022 is given by

														2022
59 13/14	53 13/14	233 13/14	55 13/14	231 13/14	57 13/14	241 13/14	52 13/14	227 13/14	61 13/14	225 13/14	63 13/14	223 13/14	229 13/14	2022
240 13/14	126 13/14	179 13/14	72 13/14	197 13/14	127 13/14	178 13/14	73 13/14	196 13/14	128 13/14	177 13/14	74 13/14	195 13/14	47 13/14	2022
48 13/14	89 13/14	180 13/14	143 13/14	162 13/14	88 13/14	181 13/14	142 13/14	163 13/14	87 13/14	182 13/14	141 13/14	164 13/14	239 13/14	2022
238 13/14	215 13/14	90 13/14	161 13/14	108 13/14	214 13/14	91 13/14	160 13/14	109 13/14	213 13/14	92 13/14	159 13/14	110 13/14	49 13/14	2022
50 13/14	144 13/14	125 13/14	198 13/14	107 13/14	145 13/14	124 13/14	199 13/14	106 13/14	146 13/14	123 13/14	200 13/14	105 13/14	237 13/14	2022
236 13/14	129 13/14	176 13/14	75 13/14	194 13/14	130 13/14	175 13/14	76 13/14	193 13/14	131 13/14	174 13/14	77 13/14	192 13/14	51 13/14	2022
222 13/14	86 13/14	183 13/14	140 13/14	165 13/14	85 13/14	184 13/14	139 13/14	166 13/14	84 13/14	185 13/14	138 13/14	167 13/14	65 13/14	2022
216 13/14	212 13/14	93 13/14	158 13/14	111 13/14	211 13/14	94 13/14	157 13/14	112 13/14	210 13/14	95 13/14	156 13/14	113 13/14	71 13/14	2022
70 13/14	147 13/14	122 13/14	201 13/14	104 13/14	148 13/14	121 13/14	202 13/14	103 13/14	149 13/14	120 13/14	203 13/14	102 13/14	217 13/14	2022
218 13/14	132 13/14	173 13/14	78 13/14	191 13/14	133 13/14	172 13/14	79 13/14	190 13/14	134 13/14	171 13/14	80 13/14	189 13/14	69 13/14	2022
68 13/14	83 13/14	186 13/14	137 13/14	168 13/14	82 13/14	187 13/14	136 13/14	169 13/14	81 13/14	188 13/14	135 13/14	170 13/14	219 13/14	2022
220 13/14	209 13/14	96 13/14	155 13/14	114 13/14	208 13/14	97 13/14	154 13/14	115 13/14	207 13/14	98 13/14	153 13/14	116 13/14	67 13/14	2022
66 13/14	150 13/14	119 13/14	204 13/14	101 13/14	151 13/14	118 13/14	205 13/14	100 13/14	152 13/14	117 13/14	206 13/14	99 13/14	221 13/14	2022
58 13/14	234 13/14	54 13/14	232 13/14	56 13/14	230 13/14	46 13/14	235 13/14	60 13/14	226 13/14	62 13/14	224 13/14	64 13/14	228 13/14	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the inner block of order 12 is a **pandigonal** magic square of order 12 with equal sums **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

2.7.3 Block Of Order 6

A **block bordered** magic square of order 14 with inner magic square of order 12 composed by blocks of order 6 with magic sum 2022 is given by

														2022
59 13/14	53 13/14	233 13/14	55 13/14	231 13/14	57 13/14	241 13/14	52 13/14	227 13/14	61 13/14	225 13/14	63 13/14	223 13/14	229 13/14	2022
240 13/14	72 13/14	208 13/14	207 13/14	200 13/14	79 13/14	95 13/14	73 13/14	209 13/14	206 13/14	201 13/14	78 13/14	94 13/14	47 13/14	2022
48 13/14	191 13/14	103 13/14	183 13/14	104 13/14	112 13/14	168 13/14	190 13/14	102 13/14	182 13/14	105 13/14	113 13/14	169 13/14	239 13/14	2022
238 13/14	167 13/14	160 13/14	128 13/14	135 13/14	151 13/14	120 13/14	166 13/14	161 13/14	129 13/14	134 13/14	150 13/14	121 13/14	49 13/14	2022
50 13/14	143 13/14	127 13/14	152 13/14	159 13/14	136 13/14	144 13/14	142 13/14	126 13/14	153 13/14	158 13/14	137 13/14	145 13/14	237 13/14	2022
236 13/14	96 13/14	175 13/14	111 13/14	176 13/14	184 13/14	119 13/14	97 13/14	174 13/14	110 13/14	177 13/14	185 13/14	118 13/14	51 13/14	2022
222 13/14	192 13/14	88 13/14	80 13/14	87 13/14	199 13/14	215 13/14	193 13/14	89 13/14	81 13/14	86 13/14	198 13/14	214 13/14	65 13/14	2022
216 13/14	74 13/14	210 13/14	205 13/14	202 13/14	77 13/14	93 13/14	75 13/14	211 13/14	204 13/14	203 13/14	76 13/14	92 13/14	71 13/14	2022
70 13/14	189 13/14	101 13/14	181 13/14	106 13/14	114 13/14	170 13/14	188 13/14	100 13/14	180 13/14	107 13/14	115 13/14	171 13/14	217 13/14	2022
218 13/14	165 13/14	162 13/14	130 13/14	133 13/14	149 13/14	122 13/14	164 13/14	163 13/14	131 13/14	132 13/14	148 13/14	123 13/14	69 13/14	2022
68 13/14	141 13/14	125 13/14	154 13/14	157 13/14	138 13/14	146 13/14	140 13/14	124 13/14	155 13/14	156 13/14	139 13/14	147 13/14	219 13/14	2022
220 13/14	98 13/14	173 13/14	109 13/14	178 13/14	186 13/14	117 13/14	99 13/14	172 13/14	108 13/14	179 13/14	187 13/14	116 13/14	67 13/14	2022
66 13/14	194 13/14	90 13/14	82 13/14	85 13/14	197 13/14	213 13/14	195 13/14	91 13/14	83 13/14	84 13/14	196 13/14	212 13/14	221 13/14	2022
58 13/14	234 13/14	54 13/14	232 13/14	56 13/14	230 13/14	46 13/14	235 13/14	60 13/14	226 13/14	62 13/14	224 13/14	64 13/14	228 13/14	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the inner block of order 12 is a magic square of order 12 with equal sums magic square of order 6.

The magic sums are $S_{14 \times 14} := 2022$, $S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12132}{7}$, $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6066}{7}$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4044}{7}$.

2.8 Bordered Magic Square of Order 15

In this case, we shall write **block-wise** magic square of order 15 with magic sum 2022 with blocks of orders 3 and 5.

2.8.1 Blocks of Order 3

A **block-wise** magic square of order 15 with block of order 3 and magic sum 2022 is given by

pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	207,8	86,8	109,8	208,8	95,8	99,8	209,8	96,8	97,8	210,8	85,8	107,8	211,8	83,8	108,8	2022
2022	101,8	214,8	87,8	110,8	204,8	88,8	111,8	202,8	89,8	100,8	212,8	90,8	98,8	213,8	91,8	2022
2022	94,8	102,8	206,8	84,8	103,8	215,8	82,8	104,8	216,8	92,8	105,8	205,8	93,8	106,8	203,8	2022
2022	57,8	221,8	124,8	58,8	230,8	114,8	59,8	231,8	112,8	60,8	220,8	122,8	61,8	218,8	123,8	2022
2022	116,8	64,8	222,8	125,8	54,8	223,8	126,8	52,8	224,8	115,8	62,8	225,8	113,8	63,8	226,8	2022
2022	229,8	117,8	56,8	219,8	118,8	65,8	217,8	119,8	66,8	227,8	120,8	55,8	228,8	121,8	53,8	2022
2022	27,8	236,8	139,8	28,8	245,8	129,8	29,8	246,8	127,8	30,8	235,8	137,8	31,8	233,8	138,8	2022
2022	131,8	34,8	237,8	140,8	24,8	238,8	141,8	22,8	239,8	130,8	32,8	240,8	128,8	33,8	241,8	2022
2022	244,8	132,8	26,8	234,8	133,8	35,8	232,8	134,8	36,8	242,8	135,8	25,8	243,8	136,8	23,8	2022
2022	177,8	71,8	154,8	178,8	80,8	144,8	179,8	81,8	142,8	180,8	70,8	152,8	181,8	68,8	153,8	2022
2022	146,8	184,8	72,8	155,8	174,8	73,8	156,8	172,8	74,8	145,8	182,8	75,8	143,8	183,8	76,8	2022
2022	79,8	147,8	176,8	69,8	148,8	185,8	67,8	149,8	186,8	77,8	150,8	175,8	78,8	151,8	173,8	2022
2022	192,8	41,8	169,8	193,8	50,8	159,8	194,8	51,8	157,8	195,8	40,8	167,8	196,8	38,8	168,8	2022
2022	161,8	199,8	42,8	170,8	189,8	43,8	171,8	187,8	44,8	160,8	197,8	45,8	158,8	198,8	46,8	2022
	49,8	162,8	191,8	39,8	163,8	200,8	37,8	164,8	201,8	47,8	165,8	190,8	48,8	166,8	188,8	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 3 are of **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{15 \times 15} := 2022$, $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{2022}{5}$

2.8.2 Blocks of Order 5

A **block-wise** magic square of order 15 with block of order 5 and magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	22,8	239,8	51,8	140,8	218,8	52,8	209,8	96,8	125,8	188,8	67,8	179,8	111,8	155,8	158,8	2022
2022	141,8	230,8	23,8	232,8	44,8	126,8	200,8	53,8	202,8	89,8	156,8	170,8	68,8	172,8	104,8	2022
2022	233,8	37,8	134,8	231,8	35,8	203,8	82,8	119,8	201,8	65,8	173,8	97,8	149,8	171,8	80,8	2022
2022	224,8	36,8	245,8	38,8	127,8	194,8	66,8	215,8	83,8	112,8	164,8	81,8	185,8	98,8	142,8	2022
2022	50,8	128,8	217,8	29,8	246,8	95,8	113,8	187,8	59,8	216,8	110,8	143,8	157,8	74,8	186,8	2022
2022	24,8	238,8	49,8	138,8	221,8	54,8	208,8	94,8	123,8	191,8	69,8	178,8	109,8	153,8	161,8	2022
2022	139,8	228,8	26,8	234,8	43,8	124,8	198,8	56,8	204,8	88,8	154,8	168,8	71,8	174,8	103,8	2022
2022	236,8	39,8	133,8	229,8	33,8	206,8	84,8	118,8	199,8	63,8	176,8	99,8	148,8	169,8	78,8	2022
2022	223,8	34,8	243,8	41,8	129,8	193,8	64,8	213,8	86,8	114,8	163,8	79,8	183,8	101,8	144,8	2022
2022	48,8	131,8	219,8	28,8	244,8	93,8	116,8	189,8	58,8	214,8	108,8	146,8	159,8	73,8	184,8	2022
2022	25,8	240,8	47,8	136,8	222,8	55,8	210,8	92,8	121,8	192,8	70,8	180,8	107,8	151,8	162,8	2022
2022	137,8	226,8	27,8	235,8	45,8	122,8	196,8	57,8	205,8	90,8	152,8	166,8	72,8	175,8	105,8	2022
2022	237,8	40,8	135,8	227,8	31,8	207,8	85,8	120,8	197,8	61,8	177,8	100,8	150,8	167,8	76,8	2022
2022	225,8	32,8	241,8	42,8	130,8	195,8	62,8	211,8	87,8	115,8	165,8	77,8	181,8	102,8	145,8	2022
	46,8	132,8	220,8	30,8	242,8	91,8	117,8	190,8	60,8	212,8	106,8	147,8	160,8	75,8	182,8	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{15 \times 15} := 2022$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 674$.

2.9 Block-Wise and Block-Bordred Magic Squares of Order 16

2.9.1 Block-Wise

A **block-wise** magic square of order 16 with blocks of order 4 and magic sum 2022 is given by

The **bordered magic square** of order 16 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

	pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	104 7/8	155 7/8	16 7/8	227 7/8	89 7/8	170 7/8	33 7/8	210 7/8	118 7/8	141 7/8	-1 1/8	245 7/8	71 7/8	188 7/8	47 7/8	196 7/8	2022
2022	19 7/8	224 7/8	107 7/8	152 7/8	34 7/8	209 7/8	90 7/8	169 7/8	5 7/8	238 7/8	125 7/8	134 7/8	52 7/8	191 7/8	76 7/8	183 7/8	2022
2022	235 7/8	24 7/8	147 7/8	96 7/8	218 7/8	41 7/8	162 7/8	81 7/8	253 7/8	6 7/8	133 7/8	110 7/8	204 7/8	55 7/8	180 7/8	63 7/8	2022
2022	144 7/8	99 7/8	232 7/8	27 7/8	161 7/8	82 7/8	217 7/8	42 7/8	126 7/8	117 7/8	246 7/8	13 7/8	175 7/8	68 7/8	199 7/8	60 7/8	2022
2022	119 7/8	140 7/8	-0,125	244 7/8	70 7/8	189 7/8	46 7/8	197 7/8	105 7/8	154 7/8	17 7/8	226 7/8	88 7/8	171 7/8	32 7/8	211 7/8	2022
2022	4 7/8	239 7/8	124 7/8	135 7/8	53 7/8	190 7/8	77 7/8	182 7/8	18 7/8	225 7/8	106 7/8	153 7/8	35 7/8	208 7/8	91 7/8	168 7/8	2022
2022	252 7/8	7 7/8	132 7/8	111 7/8	205 7/8	54 7/8	181 7/8	62 7/8	234 7/8	25 7/8	146 7/8	97 7/8	219 7/8	40 7/8	163 7/8	80 7/8	2022
2022	127 7/8	116 7/8	247 7/8	12 7/8	174 7/8	69 7/8	198 7/8	61 7/8	145 7/8	98 7/8	233 7/8	26 7/8	160 7/8	83 7/8	216 7/8	43 7/8	2022
2022	73 7/8	186 7/8	49 7/8	194 7/8	120 7/8	139 7/8	7 7/8	243 7/8	87 7/8	172 7/8	31 7/8	212 7/8	102 7/8	157 7/8	14 7/8	229 7/8	2022
2022	50 7/8	193 7/8	74 7/8	185 7/8	3 7/8	240 7/8	123 7/8	136 7/8	36 7/8	207 7/8	92 7/8	167 7/8	21 7/8	222 7/8	109 7/8	150 7/8	2022
2022	202 7/8	57 7/8	178 7/8	65 7/8	251 7/8	8 7/8	131 7/8	112 7/8	220 7/8	39 7/8	164 7/8	79 7/8	237 7/8	22 7/8	149 7/8	94 7/8	2022
2022	177 7/8	66 7/8	201 7/8	58 7/8	128 7/8	115 7/8	248 7/8	11 7/8	159 7/8	84 7/8	215 7/8	44 7/8	142 7/8	101 7/8	230 7/8	29 7/8	2022
2022	86 7/8	173 7/8	30 7/8	213 7/8	103 7/8	156 7/8	15 7/8	228 7/8	72 7/8	187 7/8	48 7/8	195 7/8	121 7/8	138 7/8	1 7/8	242 7/8	2022
2022	37 7/8	206 7/8	93 7/8	166 7/8	20 7/8	223 7/8	108 7/8	151 7/8	51 7/8	192 7/8	75 7/8	184 7/8	2 7/8	241 7/8	122 7/8	137 7/8	2022
2022	221 7/8	38 7/8	165 7/8	78 7/8	236 7/8	23 7/8	148 7/8	95 7/8	203 7/8	56 7/8	179 7/8	64 7/8	250 7/8	9 7/8	130 7/8	113 7/8	2022
	158 7/8	85 7/8	214 7/8	45 7/8	143 7/8	100 7/8	231 7/8	28 7/8	176 7/8	67 7/8	200 7/8	59 7/8	129 7/8	114 7/8	249 7/8	10 7/8	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 16. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16} := 2022$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{1011}{2}$.

2.9.2 Block-Bordered

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 16 with 4 **bordered** magic squares of order 8 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																2022
5 7/8	- 1/8	251 7/8	253 7/8	240 7/8	10 7/8	242 7/8	4 7/8	37 7/8	31 7/8	219 7/8	221 7/8	208 7/8	42 7/8	210 7/8	36 7/8	2022
2 7/8	235 7/8	233 7/8	14 7/8	239 7/8	15 7/8	17 7/8	249 7/8	34 7/8	203 7/8	201 7/8	46 7/8	207 7/8	47 7/8	49 7/8	217 7/8	2022
3 7/8	13 7/8	28 7/8	225 7/8	22 7/8	227 7/8	238 7/8	248 7/8	35 7/8	45 7/8	60 7/8	193 7/8	54 7/8	195 7/8	206 7/8	216 7/8	2022
8 7/8	19 7/8	23 7/8	226 7/8	29 7/8	224 7/8	232 7/8	243 7/8	40 7/8	51 7/8	55 7/8	194 7/8	61 7/8	192 7/8	200 7/8	211 7/8	2022
250 7/8	21 7/8	229 7/8	24 7/8	223 7/8	26 7/8	230 7/8	1 7/8	218 7/8	53 7/8	197 7/8	56 7/8	191 7/8	58 7/8	198 7/8	33 7/8	2022
245 7/8	231 7/8	222 7/8	27 7/8	228 7/8	25 7/8	20 7/8	6 7/8	213 7/8	199 7/8	190 7/8	59 7/8	196 7/8	57 7/8	52 7/8	38 7/8	2022
244 7/8	234 7/8	18 7/8	237 7/8	12 7/8	236 7/8	16 7/8	7 7/8	212 7/8	202 7/8	50 7/8	205 7/8	44 7/8	204 7/8	48 7/8	39 7/8	2022
247 7/8	252 7/8	7/8	-11/8	11 7/8	241 7/8	9 7/8	246 7/8	215 7/8	220 7/8	32 7/8	30 7/8	43 7/8	209 7/8	41 7/8	214 7/8	2022
101 7/8	95 7/8	155 7/8	157 7/8	144 7/8	106 7/8	146 7/8	100 7/8	69 7/8	63 7/8	187 7/8	189 7/8	176 7/8	74 7/8	178 7/8	68 7/8	2022
98 7/8	139 7/8	137 7/8	110 7/8	143 7/8	111 7/8	113 7/8	153 7/8	66 7/8	171 7/8	169 7/8	78 7/8	175 7/8	79 7/8	81 7/8	185 7/8	2022
99 7/8	109 7/8	124 7/8	129 7/8	118 7/8	131 7/8	142 7/8	152 7/8	67 7/8	77 7/8	92 7/8	161 7/8	86 7/8	163 7/8	174 7/8	184 7/8	2022
104 7/8	115 7/8	119 7/8	130 7/8	125 7/8	128 7/8	136 7/8	147 7/8	72 7/8	83 7/8	87 7/8	162 7/8	93 7/8	160 7/8	168 7/8	179 7/8	2022
154 7/8	117 7/8	133 7/8	120 7/8	127 7/8	122 7/8	134 7/8	97 7/8	186 7/8	85 7/8	165 7/8	88 7/8	159 7/8	90 7/8	166 7/8	65 7/8	2022
149 7/8	135 7/8	126 7/8	123 7/8	132 7/8	121 7/8	116 7/8	102 7/8	181 7/8	167 7/8	158 7/8	91 7/8	164 7/8	89 7/8	84 7/8	70 7/8	2022
148 7/8	138 7/8	114 7/8	141 7/8	108 7/8	140 7/8	112 7/8	103 7/8	180 7/8	170 7/8	82 7/8	173 7/8	76 7/8	172 7/8	80 7/8	71 7/8	2022
151 7/8	156 7/8	96 7/8	94 7/8	107 7/8	145 7/8	105 7/8	150 7/8	183 7/8	188 7/8	64 7/8	62 7/8	75 7/8	177 7/8	73 7/8	182 7/8	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the four blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 8 are of equal sums. The magic sums are $S_{16 \times 16} := 2022$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 1011$, $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3033}{4}$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{1011}{2}$.

2.10 Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 17

In this case, we shall write **block-bordred** magic square of order 17 with magic sum 2022 in two different ways.

2.10.1 Blocks of Order 3

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 for the magic sum 2022 with inner block a magic square of order 15 having blocks of order 3 is given by

																	2022
-10 1/17	261 16/17	259 16/17	257 16/17	255 16/17	253 16/17	251 16/17	249 16/17	248 16/17	-6 1/17	-4 1/17	-2 1/17	- 1/17	116/17	3 16/17	5 16/17	-8 1/17	2022
-25 1/17	191 16/17	70 16/17	93 16/17	192 16/17	79 16/17	83 16/17	193 16/17	80 16/17	81 16/17	194 16/17	69 16/17	91 16/17	195 16/17	67 16/17	92 16/17	262 16/17	2022
-23 1/17	85 16/17	198 16/17	71 16/17	94 16/17	188 16/17	72 16/17	95 16/17	186 16/17	73 16/17	84 16/17	196 16/17	74 16/17	82 16/17	197 16/17	75 16/17	260 16/17	2022
-21 1/17	78 16/17	86 16/17	190 16/17	68 16/17	87 16/17	199 16/17	66 16/17	88 16/17	200 16/17	76 16/17	89 16/17	189 16/17	77 16/17	90 16/17	187 16/17	258 16/17	2022
-19 1/17	41 16/17	205 16/17	108 16/17	42 16/17	214 16/17	98 16/17	43 16/17	215 16/17	96 16/17	44 16/17	204 16/17	106 16/17	45 16/17	202 16/17	107 16/17	256 16/17	2022
-17 1/17	100 16/17	48 16/17	206 16/17	109 16/17	38 16/17	207 16/17	110 16/17	36 16/17	208 16/17	99 16/17	46 16/17	209 16/17	97 16/17	47 16/17	210 16/17	254 16/17	2022
-15 1/17	213 16/17	101 16/17	40 16/17	203 16/17	102 16/17	49 16/17	201 16/17	103 16/17	50 16/17	211 16/17	104 16/17	39 16/17	212 16/17	105 16/17	37 16/17	252 16/17	2022
-13 1/17	11 16/17	220 16/17	123 16/17	12 16/17	229 16/17	113 16/17	13 16/17	230 16/17	111 16/17	14 16/17	219 16/17	121 16/17	15 16/17	217 16/17	122 16/17	250 16/17	2022
246 16/17	115 16/17	18 16/17	221 16/17	124 16/17	8 16/17	222 16/17	125 16/17	6 16/17	223 16/17	114 16/17	16 16/17	224 16/17	112 16/17	17 16/17	225 16/17	-9 1/17	2022
244 16/17	228 16/17	116 16/17	10 16/17	218 16/17	117 16/17	19 16/17	216 16/17	118 16/17	20 16/17	226 16/17	119 16/17	9 16/17	227 16/17	120 16/17	7 16/17	-7 1/17	2022
242 16/17	161 16/17	55 16/17	138 16/17	162 16/17	64 16/17	128 16/17	163 16/17	65 16/17	126 16/17	164 16/17	54 16/17	136 16/17	165 16/17	52 16/17	137 16/17	-5 1/17	2022
240 16/17	130 16/17	168 16/17	56 16/17	139 16/17	158 16/17	57 16/17	140 16/17	156 16/17	58 16/17	129 16/17	166 16/17	59 16/17	127 16/17	167 16/17	60 16/17	-3 1/17	2022
238 16/17	63 16/17	131 16/17	160 16/17	53 16/17	132 16/17	169 16/17	51 16/17	133 16/17	170 16/17	61 16/17	134 16/17	159 16/17	62 16/17	135 16/17	157 16/17	-1 1/17	2022
236 16/17	176 16/17	25 16/17	153 16/17	177 16/17	34 16/17	143 16/17	178 16/17	35 16/17	141 16/17	179 16/17	24 16/17	151 16/17	180 16/17	22 16/17	152 16/17	16/17	2022
234 16/17	145 16/17	183 16/17	26 16/17	154 16/17	173 16/17	27 16/17	155 16/17	171 16/17	28 16/17	144 16/17	181 16/17	29 16/17	142 16/17	182 16/17	30 16/17	2 16/17	2022
232 16/17	33 16/17	146 16/17	175 16/17	23 16/17	147 16/17	184 16/17	21 16/17	148 16/17	185 16/17	31 16/17	149 16/17	174 16/17	32 16/17	150 16/17	172 16/17	4 16/17	2022
245 16/17	-24 1/17	-22 1/17	-20 1/17	-18 1/17	-16 1/17	-14 1/17	-12 1/17	-11 1/17	243 16/17	241 16/17	239 16/17	237 16/17	235 16/17	233 16/17	231 16/17	247 16/17	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 3 are of **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{17 \times 17} := 2022$, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30330}{17}$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{6066}{17}$

2.10.2 Blocks of Order 5

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 for the magic sum 2022 with inner block a magic square of order 15 having blocks of order 5 is given by

																		2022
-10 1/17	261 16/17	259 16/17	257 16/17	255 16/17	253 16/17	251 16/17	249 16/17	248 16/17	-6 1/17	-4 1/17	-2 1/17	- 1/17	1 16/17	3 16/17	5 16/17	-8 1/17	2022	
-25 1/17	6 16/17	223 16/17	35 16/17	124 16/17	202 16/17	36 16/17	193 16/17	80 16/17	109 16/17	172 16/17	51 16/17	163 16/17	95 16/17	139 16/17	142 16/17	262 16/17	2022	
-23 1/17	125 16/17	214 16/17	7 16/17	216 16/17	28 16/17	110 16/17	184 16/17	37 16/17	186 16/17	73 16/17	140 16/17	154 16/17	52 16/17	156 16/17	88 16/17	260 16/17	2022	
-21 1/17	217 16/17	21 16/17	118 16/17	215 16/17	19 16/17	187 16/17	66 16/17	103 16/17	185 16/17	49 16/17	157 16/17	81 16/17	133 16/17	155 16/17	64 16/17	258 16/17	2022	
-19 1/17	208 16/17	20 16/17	229 16/17	22 16/17	111 16/17	178 16/17	50 16/17	199 16/17	67 16/17	96 16/17	148 16/17	65 16/17	169 16/17	82 16/17	126 16/17	256 16/17	2022	
-17 1/17	34 16/17	112 16/17	201 16/17	13 16/17	230 16/17	79 16/17	97 16/17	171 16/17	43 16/17	200 16/17	94 16/17	127 16/17	141 16/17	58 16/17	170 16/17	254 16/17	2022	
-15 1/17	8 16/17	222 16/17	33 16/17	122 16/17	205 16/17	38 16/17	192 16/17	78 16/17	107 16/17	175 16/17	53 16/17	162 16/17	93 16/17	137 16/17	145 16/17	252 16/17	2022	
-13 1/17	123 16/17	212 16/17	10 16/17	218 16/17	27 16/17	108 16/17	182 16/17	40 16/17	188 16/17	72 16/17	138 16/17	152 16/17	55 16/17	158 16/17	87 16/17	250 16/17	2022	
246 16/17	220 16/17	23 16/17	117 16/17	213 16/17	17 16/17	190 16/17	68 16/17	102 16/17	183 16/17	47 16/17	160 16/17	83 16/17	132 16/17	153 16/17	62 16/17	-9 1/17	2022	
244 16/17	207 16/17	18 16/17	227 16/17	25 16/17	113 16/17	177 16/17	48 16/17	197 16/17	70 16/17	98 16/17	147 16/17	63 16/17	167 16/17	85 16/17	128 16/17	-7 1/17	2022	
242 16/17	32 16/17	115 16/17	203 16/17	12 16/17	228 16/17	77 16/17	100 16/17	173 16/17	42 16/17	198 16/17	92 16/17	130 16/17	143 16/17	57 16/17	168 16/17	-5 1/17	2022	
240 16/17	9 16/17	224 16/17	31 16/17	120 16/17	206 16/17	39 16/17	194 16/17	76 16/17	105 16/17	176 16/17	54 16/17	164 16/17	91 16/17	135 16/17	146 16/17	-3 1/17	2022	
238 16/17	121 16/17	210 16/17	11 16/17	219 16/17	29 16/17	106 16/17	180 16/17	41 16/17	189 16/17	74 16/17	136 16/17	150 16/17	56 16/17	159 16/17	89 16/17	-1 1/17	2022	
236 16/17	221 16/17	24 16/17	119 16/17	211 16/17	15 16/17	191 16/17	69 16/17	104 16/17	181 16/17	45 16/17	161 16/17	84 16/17	134 16/17	151 16/17	60 16/17	16/17	2022	
234 16/17	209 16/17	16 16/17	225 16/17	26 16/17	114 16/17	179 16/17	46 16/17	195 16/17	71 16/17	99 16/17	149 16/17	61 16/17	165 16/17	86 16/17	129 16/17	2 16/17	2022	
232 16/17	30 16/17	116 16/17	204 16/17	14 16/17	226 16/17	75 16/17	101 16/17	174 16/17	44 16/17	196 16/17	90 16/17	131 16/17	144 16/17	59 16/17	166 16/17	4 16/17	2022	
245 16/17	-24 1/17	-22 1/17	-20 1/17	-18 1/17	-16 1/17	-14 1/17	-12 1/17	-11 1/17	243 16/17	241 16/17	239 16/17	237 16/17	235 16/17	233 16/17	231 16/17	247 16/17	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of equal sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{17 \times 17} := 2022$, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30330}{17}$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10110}{17}$.

2.11 Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 18

In this case, we shall give four types magic squares of order 18 with magic sum 2022.

2.11.1 Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 3

A **block-wise** magic square of order 18 with blocks of order 3 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																			2022
-31 5/6	-11 1/6	-48 1/6	142 5/6	126 5/6	161 5/6	195 5/6	211 5/6	176 5/6	249 5/6	229 5/6	266 5/6	88 5/6	108 5/6	71 5/6	27 5/6	7 5/6	44 5/6	2022	
-47 1/6	-30 1/6	-13 1/6	162 5/6	143 5/6	124 5/6	175 5/6	194 5/6	213 5/6	265 5/6	248 5/6	231 5/6	72 5/6	89 5/6	106 5/6	43 5/6	26 5/6	9 5/6	2022	
-12 1/6	-49 1/6	-29 1/6	125 5/6	160 5/6	144 5/6	212 5/6	177 5/6	193 5/6	230 5/6	267 5/6	247 5/6	107 5/6	70 5/6	90 5/6	8 5/6	45 5/6	25 5/6	2022	
196 5/6	216 5/6	179 5/6	22 5/6	6 5/6	41 5/6	250 5/6	234 5/6	269 5/6	81 5/6	97 5/6	62 5/6	136 5/6	120 5/6	155 5/6	-19 1/6	5/6	-36 1/6	2022	
180 5/6	197 5/6	214 5/6	42 5/6	23 5/6	4 5/6	270 5/6	251 5/6	232 5/6	61 5/6	80 5/6	99 5/6	156 5/6	137 5/6	118 5/6	-35 1/6	-18 1/6	-11 1/6	2022	
215 5/6	178 5/6	198 5/6	5 5/6	40 5/6	24 5/6	233 5/6	268 5/6	252 5/6	98 5/6	63 5/6	79 5/6	119 5/6	154 5/6	138 5/6	-1/6	-37 1/6	-17 1/6	2022	
39 5/6	19 5/6	56 5/6	-14 1/6	1 5/6	-33 1/6	76 5/6	96 5/6	59 5/6	190 5/6	210 5/6	173 5/6	238 5/6	222 5/6	257 5/6	141 5/6	121 5/6	158 5/6	2022	
55 5/6	38 5/6	21 5/6	-34 1/6	-15 1/6	3 5/6	60 5/6	77 5/6	94 5/6	174 5/6	191 5/6	208 5/6	258 5/6	239 5/6	220 5/6	157 5/6	140 5/6	123 5/6	2022	
20 5/6	57 5/6	37 5/6	2 5/6	-32 1/6	-16 1/6	95 5/6	58 5/6	78 5/6	209 5/6	172 5/6	192 5/6	221 5/6	256 5/6	240 5/6	122 5/6	159 5/6	139 5/6	2022	
243 5/6	223 5/6	260 5/6	87 5/6	103 5/6	68 5/6	-20 1/6	-4 1/6	-39 1/6	147 5/6	127 5/6	164 5/6	33 5/6	13 5/6	50 5/6	184 5/6	204 5/6	167 5/6	2022	
259 5/6	242 5/6	225 5/6	67 5/6	86 5/6	105 5/6	-40 1/6	-21 1/6	-2 1/6	163 5/6	146 5/6	129 5/6	49 5/6	32 5/6	15 5/6	168 5/6	185 5/6	202 5/6	2022	
224 5/6	261 5/6	241 5/6	104 5/6	69 5/6	85 5/6	-3 1/6	-38 1/6	-22 1/6	128 5/6	165 5/6	145 5/6	14 5/6	51 5/6	31 5/6	203 5/6	166 5/6	186 5/6	2022	
130 5/6	114 5/6	149 5/6	244 5/6	228 5/6	263 5/6	34 5/6	18 5/6	53 5/6	-25 1/6	-5 1/6	-42 1/6	201 5/6	217 5/6	182 5/6	82 5/6	102 5/6	65 5/6	2022	
150 5/6	131 5/6	112 5/6	264 5/6	245 5/6	226 5/6	54 5/6	35 5/6	16 5/6	-41 1/6	-24 1/6	-7 1/6	181 5/6	200 5/6	219 5/6	66 5/6	83 5/6	100 5/6	2022	
113 5/6	148 5/6	132 5/6	227 5/6	262 5/6	246 5/6	17 5/6	52 5/6	36 5/6	-6 1/6	-43 1/6	-23 1/6	218 5/6	183 5/6	199 5/6	101 5/6	64 5/6	84 5/6	2022	
93 5/6	109 5/6	74 5/6	189 5/6	205 5/6	170 5/6	135 5/6	115 5/6	152 5/6	28 5/6	12 5/6	47 5/6	-26 1/6	-10 1/6	-45 1/6	255 5/6	235 5/6	272 5/6	2022	
73 5/6	92 5/6	111 5/6	169 5/6	188 5/6	207 5/6	151 5/6	134 5/6	117 5/6	48 5/6	29 5/6	10 5/6	-46 1/6	-27 1/6	-8 1/6	271 5/6	254 5/6	237 5/6	2022	
110 5/6	75 5/6	91 5/6	206 5/6	171 5/6	187 5/6	116 5/6	153 5/6	133 5/6	11 5/6	46 5/6	30 5/6	-9 1/6	-44 1/6	-28 1/6	236 5/6	273 5/6	253 5/6	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the magic squares of order 3 are of different magic sums.

2.11.2 Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 6

A **block-wise** magic square of order 18 with blocks of order 6 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																			2022
-31 1/6	-11 1/6	-48 1/6	142 5/6	126 5/6	161 5/6	195 5/6	211 5/6	176 5/6	249 5/6	229 5/6	266 5/6	88 5/6	108 5/6	71 5/6	27 5/6	7 5/6	44 5/6	2022	
-47 1/6	-30 1/6	-13 1/6	162 5/6	143 5/6	124 5/6	175 5/6	194 5/6	213 5/6	265 5/6	248 5/6	231 5/6	72 5/6	89 5/6	106 5/6	43 5/6	26 5/6	9 5/6	2022	
-12 1/6	-49 1/6	-29 1/6	125 5/6	160 5/6	144 5/6	212 5/6	177 5/6	193 5/6	230 5/6	267 5/6	247 5/6	107 5/6	70 5/6	90 5/6	8 5/6	45 5/6	25 5/6	2022	
196 5/6	216 5/6	179 5/6	22 5/6	6 5/6	41 5/6	250 5/6	234 5/6	269 5/6	81 5/6	97 5/6	62 5/6	136 5/6	120 5/6	155 5/6	-19 1/6	5/6	-36 1/6	2022	
180 5/6	197 5/6	214 5/6	42 5/6	23 5/6	4 5/6	270 5/6	251 5/6	232 5/6	61 5/6	80 5/6	99 5/6	156 5/6	137 5/6	118 5/6	-35 1/6	-18 1/6	-11 1/6	2022	
215 5/6	178 5/6	198 5/6	5 5/6	40 5/6	24 5/6	233 5/6	268 5/6	252 5/6	98 5/6	63 5/6	79 5/6	119 5/6	154 5/6	138 5/6	-1/6	-37 1/6	-17 1/6	2022	
39 5/6	19 5/6	56 5/6	-14 1/6	1 5/6	-33 1/6	76 5/6	96 5/6	59 5/6	190 5/6	210 5/6	173 5/6	238 5/6	222 5/6	257 5/6	141 5/6	121 5/6	158 5/6	2022	
55 5/6	38 5/6	21 5/6	-34 1/6	-15 1/6	3 5/6	60 5/6	77 5/6	94 5/6	174 5/6	191 5/6	208 5/6	258 5/6	239 5/6	220 5/6	157 5/6	140 5/6	123 5/6	2022	
20 5/6	57 5/6	37 5/6	2 5/6	-32 1/6	-16 1/6	95 5/6	58 5/6	78 5/6	209 5/6	172 5/6	192 5/6	221 5/6	256 5/6	240 5/6	122 5/6	159 5/6	139 5/6	2022	
243 5/6	223 5/6	260 5/6	87 5/6	103 5/6	68 5/6	-20 1/6	-4 1/6	-39 1/6	147 5/6	127 5/6	164 5/6	33 5/6	13 5/6	50 5/6	184 5/6	204 5/6	167 5/6	2022	
259 5/6	242 5/6	225 5/6	67 5/6	86 5/6	105 5/6	-40 1/6	-21 1/6	-2 1/6	163 5/6	146 5/6	129 5/6	49 5/6	32 5/6	15 5/6	168 5/6	185 5/6	202 5/6	2022	
224 5/6	261 5/6	241 5/6	104 5/6	69 5/6	85 5/6	-3 1/6	-38 1/6	-22 1/6	128 5/6	165 5/6	145 5/6	14 5/6	51 5/6	31 5/6	203 5/6	166 5/6	186 5/6	2022	
130 5/6	114 5/6	149 5/6	244 5/6	228 5/6	263 5/6	34 5/6	18 5/6	53 5/6	-25 1/6	-5 1/6	-42 1/6	201 5/6	217 5/6	182 5/6	82 5/6	102 5/6	65 5/6	2022	
150 5/6	131 5/6	112 5/6	264 5/6	245 5/6	226 5/6	54 5/6	35 5/6	16 5/6	-41 1/6	-24 1/6	-7 1/6	181 5/6	200 5/6	219 5/6	66 5/6	83 5/6	100 5/6	2022	
113 5/6	148 5/6	132 5/6	227 5/6	262 5/6	246 5/6	17 5/6	52 5/6	36 5/6	-6 1/6	-43 1/6	-23 1/6	218 5/6	183 5/6	199 5/6	101 5/6	64 5/6	84 5/6	2022	
93 5/6	109 5/6	74 5/6	189 5/6	205 5/6	170 5/6	135 5/6	115 5/6	152 5/6	28 5/6	12 5/6	47 5/6	-26 1/6	-10 1/6	-45 1/6	255 5/6	235 5/6	272 5/6	2022	
73 5/6	92 5/6	111 5/6	169 5/6	188 5/6	207 5/6	151 5/6	134 5/6	117 5/6	48 5/6	29 5/6	10 5/6	-46 1/6	-27 1/6	-8 1/6	271 5/6	254 5/6	237 5/6	2022	
110 5/6	75 5/6	91 5/6	206 5/6	171 5/6	187 5/6	116 5/6	153 5/6	133 5/6	11 5/6	46 5/6	30 5/6	-9 1/6	-44 1/6	-28 1/6	236 5/6	273 5/6	253 5/6	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the magic squares of order 6 are of equal magic sums. The magic sums are $S_{18 \times 18} := 2022$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 674$.

2.11.3 Block-Bordered With Blocks of Order 4

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 18 with blocks of order 4 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																			2022
256 5/6	-25 1/6	250 5/6	-27 1/6	252 5/6	-29 1/6	254 5/6	-31 1/6	265 5/6	-49 1/6	258 5/6	-35 1/6	260 5/6	-37 1/6	262 5/6	-39 1/6	264 5/6	-33 1/6	2022	
247 5/6	90 5/6	141 5/6	2 5/6	213 5/6	75 5/6	156 5/6	19 5/6	196 5/6	104 5/6	127 5/6	-15 1/6	231 5/6	57 5/6	174 5/6	33 5/6	182 5/6	-23 1/6	2022	
-22 1/6	5 5/6	210 5/6	93 5/6	138 5/6	20 5/6	195 5/6	76 5/6	155 5/6	-8 1/6	224 5/6	111 5/6	120 5/6	38 5/6	177 5/6	62 5/6	169 5/6	246 5/6	2022	
245 5/6	221 5/6	10 5/6	133 5/6	82 5/6	204 5/6	27 5/6	148 5/6	67 5/6	239 5/6	-7 1/6	119 5/6	96 5/6	190 5/6	41 5/6	166 5/6	49 5/6	-21 1/6	2022	
-20 1/6	130 5/6	85 5/6	218 5/6	13 5/6	147 5/6	68 5/6	203 5/6	28 5/6	112 5/6	103 5/6	232 5/6	- 1/6	161 5/6	54 5/6	185 5/6	46 5/6	244 5/6	2022	
243 5/6	105 5/6	126 5/6	-14 1/6	230 5/6	56 5/6	175 5/6	32 5/6	183 5/6	91 5/6	140 5/6	3 5/6	212 5/6	74 5/6	157 5/6	18 5/6	197 5/6	-19 1/6	2022	
-18 1/6	-9 1/6	225 5/6	110 5/6	121 5/6	39 5/6	176 5/6	63 5/6	168 5/6	4 5/6	211 5/6	92 5/6	139 5/6	21 5/6	194 5/6	77 5/6	154 5/6	242 5/6	2022	
241 5/6	238 5/6	-6 1/6	118 5/6	97 5/6	191 5/6	40 5/6	167 5/6	48 5/6	220 5/6	11 5/6	132 5/6	83 5/6	205 5/6	26 5/6	149 5/6	66 5/6	-17 1/6	2022	
-16 1/6	113 5/6	102 5/6	233 5/6	-11/6	160 5/6	55 5/6	184 5/6	47 5/6	131 5/6	84 5/6	219 5/6	12 5/6	146 5/6	69 5/6	202 5/6	29 5/6	240 5/6	2022	
-24 1/6	59 5/6	172 5/6	35 5/6	180 5/6	106 5/6	125 5/6	-13 1/6	229 5/6	73 5/6	158 5/6	17 5/6	198 5/6	88 5/6	143 5/6	5/6	215 5/6	248 5/6	2022	
-42 1/6	36 5/6	179 5/6	60 5/6	171 5/6	-10 1/6	226 5/6	109 5/6	122 5/6	22 5/6	193 5/6	78 5/6	153 5/6	7 5/6	208 5/6	95 5/6	136 5/6	266 5/6	2022	
267 5/6	188 5/6	43 5/6	164 5/6	51 5/6	237 5/6	-5 1/6	117 5/6	98 5/6	206 5/6	25 5/6	150 5/6	65 5/6	223 5/6	8 5/6	135 5/6	80 5/6	-43 1/6	2022	
-44 1/6	163 5/6	52 5/6	187 5/6	44 5/6	114 5/6	101 5/6	234 5/6	-2 1/6	145 5/6	70 5/6	201 5/6	30 5/6	128 5/6	87 5/6	216 5/6	15 5/6	268 5/6	2022	
269 5/6	72 5/6	159 5/6	16 5/6	199 5/6	89 5/6	142 5/6	1 5/6	214 5/6	58 5/6	173 5/6	34 5/6	181 5/6	107 5/6	124 5/6	-12 1/6	228 5/6	-45 1/6	2022	
-46 1/6	23 5/6	192 5/6	79 5/6	152 5/6	6 5/6	209 5/6	94 5/6	137 5/6	37 5/6	178 5/6	61 5/6	170 5/6	-11 1/6	227 5/6	108 5/6	123 5/6	270 5/6	2022	
271 5/6	207 5/6	24 5/6	151 5/6	64 5/6	222 5/6	9 5/6	134 5/6	81 5/6	189 5/6	42 5/6	165 5/6	50 5/6	236 5/6	-4 1/6	116 5/6	99 5/6	-47 1/6	2022	
-48 1/6	144 5/6	71 5/6	200 5/6	31 5/6	129 5/6	86 5/6	217 5/6	14 5/6	162 5/6	53 5/6	186 5/6	45 5/6	115 5/6	100 5/6	235 5/6	-3 1/6	272 5/6	2022	
257 5/6	249 5/6	-26 1/6	251 5/6	-28 1/6	253 5/6	-30 1/6	255 5/6	-41 1/6	273 5/6	-34 1/6	259 5/6	-36 1/6	261 5/6	-38 1/6	263 5/6	-40 1/6	-32 1/6	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the inner **pandiagonal** magic square of order 16 is with equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The magic sums are $S_{18 \times 18} := 2022$, $S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{5392}{3}$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{1348}{3}$.

2.11.4 Block-Bordered With Blocks of Order 8

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 18 with bordered magic squares of order 8 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																		2022
256 5/6	-25 1/6	250 5/6	-27 1/6	252 5/6	-29 1/6	254 5/6	-31 1/6	265 5/6	-49 1/6	258 5/6	-35 1/6	260 5/6	-37 1/6	262 5/6	-39 1/6	264 5/6	-33 1/6	2022
247 5/6	-8 1/6	-14 1/6	237 5/6	239 5/6	226 5/6	-3 1/6	228 5/6	-9 1/6	23 5/6	17 5/6	205 5/6	207 5/6	194 5/6	28 5/6	196 5/6	22 5/6	-23 1/6	2022
-22 1/6	-11 1/6	221 5/6	219 5/6	5/6	225 5/6	1 5/6	3 5/6	235 5/6	20 5/6	189 5/6	187 5/6	32 5/6	193 5/6	33 5/6	35 5/6	203 5/6	246 5/6	2022
245 5/6	-10 1/6	-1/6	14 5/6	211 5/6	8 5/6	213 5/6	224 5/6	234 5/6	21 5/6	31 5/6	46 5/6	179 5/6	40 5/6	181 5/6	192 5/6	202 5/6	-21 1/6	2022
-20 1/6	-5 1/6	5 5/6	9 5/6	212 5/6	15 5/6	210 5/6	218 5/6	229 5/6	26 5/6	37 5/6	41 5/6	180 5/6	47 5/6	178 5/6	186 5/6	197 5/6	244 5/6	2022
243 5/6	236 5/6	7 5/6	215 5/6	10 5/6	209 5/6	12 5/6	216 5/6	-12 1/6	204 5/6	39 5/6	183 5/6	42 5/6	177 5/6	44 5/6	184 5/6	19 5/6	-19 1/6	2022
-18 1/6	231 5/6	217 5/6	208 5/6	13 5/6	214 5/6	11 5/6	6 5/6	-7 1/6	199 5/6	185 5/6	176 5/6	45 5/6	182 5/6	43 5/6	38 5/6	24 5/6	242 5/6	2022
241 5/6	230 5/6	220 5/6	4 5/6	223 5/6	-11/6	222 5/6	2 5/6	-6 1/6	198 5/6	188 5/6	36 5/6	191 5/6	30 5/6	190 5/6	34 5/6	25 5/6	-17 1/6	2022
-16 1/6	233 5/6	238 5/6	-13 1/6	-15 1/6	-2 1/6	227 5/6	-4 1/6	232 5/6	201 5/6	206 5/6	18 5/6	16 5/6	29 5/6	195 5/6	27 5/6	200 5/6	240 5/6	2022
-24 1/6	87 5/6	81 5/6	141 5/6	143 5/6	130 5/6	92 5/6	132 5/6	86 5/6	55 5/6	49 5/6	173 5/6	175 5/6	162 5/6	60 5/6	164 5/6	54 5/6	248 5/6	2022
-42 1/6	84 5/6	125 5/6	123 5/6	96 5/6	129 5/6	97 5/6	99 5/6	139 5/6	52 5/6	157 5/6	155 5/6	64 5/6	161 5/6	65 5/6	67 5/6	171 5/6	266 5/6	2022
267 5/6	85 5/6	95 5/6	110 5/6	115 5/6	104 5/6	117 5/6	128 5/6	138 5/6	53 5/6	63 5/6	78 5/6	147 5/6	72 5/6	149 5/6	160 5/6	170 5/6	-43 1/6	2022
-44 1/6	90 5/6	101 5/6	105 5/6	116 5/6	111 5/6	114 5/6	122 5/6	133 5/6	58 5/6	69 5/6	73 5/6	148 5/6	79 5/6	146 5/6	154 5/6	165 5/6	268 5/6	2022
269 5/6	140 5/6	103 5/6	119 5/6	106 5/6	113 5/6	108 5/6	120 5/6	83 5/6	172 5/6	71 5/6	151 5/6	74 5/6	145 5/6	76 5/6	152 5/6	51 5/6	-45 1/6	2022
-46 1/6	135 5/6	121 5/6	112 5/6	109 5/6	118 5/6	107 5/6	102 5/6	88 5/6	167 5/6	153 5/6	144 5/6	77 5/6	150 5/6	75 5/6	70 5/6	56 5/6	270 5/6	2022
271 5/6	134 5/6	124 5/6	100 5/6	127 5/6	94 5/6	126 5/6	98 5/6	89 5/6	166 5/6	156 5/6	68 5/6	159 5/6	62 5/6	158 5/6	66 5/6	57 5/6	-47 1/6	2022
-48 1/6	137 5/6	142 5/6	82 5/6	80 5/6	93 5/6	131 5/6	91 5/6	136 5/6	169 5/6	174 5/6	50 5/6	48 5/6	61 5/6	163 5/6	59 5/6	168 5/6	272 5/6	2022
257 5/6	249 5/6	-26 1/6	251 5/6	-28 1/6	253 5/6	-30 1/6	255 5/6	-41 1/6	273 5/6	-34 1/6	259 5/6	-36 1/6	261 5/6	-38 1/6	263 5/6	-40 1/6	-32 1/6	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case, the inner **pandiagonal** magic square of order 16 is with equal sums **bordered** magic squares of order 8. The magic sums are $S_{18 \times 18} := 2022$, $S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{5392}{3}$, $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{2696}{3}$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 674$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{1348}{3}$.

2.12 Bordered Magic Square of Order 19

In this case, we shall write in two different ways a **block-bordred** magic square of order 19 with magic sum 2022.

2.12.1 Blocks of Order 3

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 for the magic sum 2022 with inner block a magic square of order 15 having blocks of order 3 is given by

2022

-54 11/19	-38 11/19	-40 11/19	-42 11/19	-44 11/19	-46 11/19	-48 11/19	-50 11/19	-52 11/19	270 8/19	271 8/19	273 8/19	275 8/19	277 8/19	279 8/19	281 8/19	283 8/19	285 8/19	-56 11/19	2022
286 8/19	-22 11/19	249 8/19	247 8/19	245 8/19	243 8/19	241 8/19	239 8/19	237 8/19	236 8/19	-18 11/19	-16 11/19	-14 11/19	-12 11/19	-10 11/19	-8 11/19	-6 11/19	-20 11/19	-73 11/19	2022
284 8/19	-37 11/19	179 8/19	58 8/19	81 8/19	180 8/19	67 8/19	71 8/19	181 8/19	68 8/19	69 8/19	182 8/19	57 8/19	79 8/19	183 8/19	55 8/19	80 8/19	250 8/19	-71 11/19	2022
282 8/19	-35 11/19	73 8/19	186 8/19	59 8/19	82 8/19	176 8/19	60 8/19	83 8/19	174 8/19	61 8/19	72 8/19	184 8/19	62 8/19	70 8/19	185 8/19	63 8/19	248 8/19	-69 11/19	2022
280 8/19	-33 11/19	66 8/19	74 8/19	178 8/19	56 8/19	75 8/19	187 8/19	54 8/19	76 8/19	188 8/19	64 8/19	77 8/19	177 8/19	65 8/19	78 8/19	175 8/19	246 8/19	-67 11/19	2022
278 8/19	-31 11/19	29 8/19	193 8/19	96 8/19	30 8/19	202 8/19	86 8/19	31 8/19	203 8/19	84 8/19	32 8/19	192 8/19	94 8/19	33 8/19	190 8/19	95 8/19	244 8/19	-65 11/19	2022
276 8/19	-29 11/19	88 8/19	36 8/19	194 8/19	97 8/19	26 8/19	195 8/19	98 8/19	24 8/19	196 8/19	87 8/19	34 8/19	197 8/19	85 8/19	35 8/19	198 8/19	242 8/19	-63 11/19	2022
274 8/19	-27 11/19	201 8/19	89 8/19	28 8/19	191 8/19	90 8/19	37 8/19	189 8/19	91 8/19	38 8/19	199 8/19	92 8/19	27 8/19	200 8/19	93 8/19	25 8/19	240 8/19	-61 11/19	2022
272 8/19	-25 11/19	-11/19	208 8/19	111 8/19	8/19	217 8/19	101 8/19	1 8/19	218 8/19	99 8/19	2 8/19	207 8/19	109 8/19	3 8/19	205 8/19	110 8/19	238 8/19	-59 11/19	2022
-55 11/19	234 8/19	103 8/19	6 8/19	209 8/19	112 8/19	-3 11/19	210 8/19	113 8/19	-5 11/19	211 8/19	102 8/19	4 8/19	212 8/19	100 8/19	5 8/19	213 8/19	-21 11/19	268 8/19	2022
-53 11/19	232 8/19	216 8/19	104 8/19	-1 11/19	206 8/19	105 8/19	7 8/19	204 8/19	106 8/19	8 8/19	214 8/19	107 8/19	-2 11/19	215 8/19	108 8/19	-4 11/19	-19 11/19	266 8/19	2022
-51 11/19	230 8/19	149 8/19	43 8/19	126 8/19	150 8/19	52 8/19	116 8/19	151 8/19	53 8/19	114 8/19	152 8/19	42 8/19	124 8/19	153 8/19	40 8/19	125 8/19	-17 11/19	264 8/19	2022
-49 11/19	228 8/19	118 8/19	156 8/19	44 8/19	127 8/19	146 8/19	45 8/19	128 8/19	144 8/19	46 8/19	117 8/19	154 8/19	47 8/19	115 8/19	155 8/19	48 8/19	-15 11/19	262 8/19	2022
-47 11/19	226 8/19	51 8/19	119 8/19	148 8/19	41 8/19	120 8/19	157 8/19	39 8/19	121 8/19	158 8/19	49 8/19	122 8/19	147 8/19	50 8/19	123 8/19	145 8/19	-13 11/19	260 8/19	2022
-45 11/19	224 8/19	164 8/19	13 8/19	141 8/19	165 8/19	22 8/19	131 8/19	166 8/19	23 8/19	129 8/19	167 8/19	12 8/19	139 8/19	168 8/19	10 8/19	140 8/19	-11 11/19	258 8/19	2022
-43 11/19	222 8/19	133 8/19	171 8/19	14 8/19	142 8/19	161 8/19	15 8/19	143 8/19	159 8/19	16 8/19	132 8/19	169 8/19	17 8/19	130 8/19	170 8/19	18 8/19	-9 11/19	256 8/19	2022
-41 11/19	220 8/19	21 8/19	134 8/19	163 8/19	11 8/19	135 8/19	172 8/19	9 8/19	136 8/19	173 8/19	19 8/19	137 8/19	162 8/19	20 8/19	138 8/19	160 8/19	-7 11/19	254 8/19	2022
-39 11/19	233 8/19	-36 11/19	-34 11/19	-32 11/19	-30 11/19	-28 11/19	-26 11/19	-24 11/19	-23 11/19	231 8/19	229 8/19	227 8/19	225 8/19	223 8/19	221 8/19	219 8/19	235 8/19	252 8/19	2022
269 8/19	251 8/19	253 8/19	255 8/19	257 8/19	259 8/19	261 8/19	263 8/19	265 8/19	-57 11/19	-58 11/19	-60 11/19	-62 11/19	-64 11/19	-66 11/19	-68 11/19	-70 11/19	-72 11/19	267 8/19	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 3 are of **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{19 \times 19} := 2022$, $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{34374}{19}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30330}{19}$ and $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{6066}{19}$

2.12.2 Blocks of Order 5

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 for the magic sum 2022 with inner block a magic square of order 15 having blocks of order 5 is given by

2022

-54 11/19	-38 11/19	-40 11/19	-42 11/19	-44 11/19	-46 11/19	-48 11/19	-50 11/19	-52 11/19	270 8/19	271 8/19	273 8/19	275 8/19	277 8/19	279 8/19	281 8/19	283 8/19	285 8/19	-56 11/19	2022
286 8/19	-22 11/19	249 8/19	247 8/19	245 8/19	243 8/19	241 8/19	239 8/19	237 8/19	236 8/19	-18 11/19	-16 11/19	-14 11/19	-12 11/19	-10 11/19	-8 11/19	-6 11/19	-20 11/19	-73 11/19	2022
284 8/19	-37 11/19	-5 11/19	211 8/19	23 8/19	112 8/19	190 8/19	24 8/19	181 8/19	68 8/19	97 8/19	160 8/19	39 8/19	151 8/19	83 8/19	127 8/19	130 8/19	250 8/19	-71 11/19	2022
282 8/19	-35 11/19	113 8/19	202 8/19	-4 11/19	204 8/19	16 8/19	98 8/19	172 8/19	25 8/19	174 8/19	61 8/19	128 8/19	142 8/19	40 8/19	144 8/19	76 8/19	248 8/19	-69 11/19	2022
280 8/19	-33 11/19	205 8/19	9 8/19	106 8/19	203 8/19	7 8/19	175 8/19	54 8/19	91 8/19	173 8/19	37 8/19	145 8/19	69 8/19	121 8/19	143 8/19	52 8/19	246 8/19	-67 11/19	2022
278 8/19	-31 11/19	196 8/19	8 8/19	217 8/19	10 8/19	99 8/19	166 8/19	38 8/19	187 8/19	55 8/19	84 8/19	136 8/19	53 8/19	157 8/19	70 8/19	114 8/19	244 8/19	-65 11/19	2022
276 8/19	-29 11/19	22 8/19	100 8/19	189 8/19	1 8/19	218 8/19	67 8/19	85 8/19	159 8/19	31 8/19	188 8/19	82 8/19	115 8/19	129 8/19	46 8/19	158 8/19	242 8/19	-63 11/19	2022
274 8/19	-27 11/19	-3 11/19	210 8/19	21 8/19	110 8/19	193 8/19	26 8/19	180 8/19	66 8/19	95 8/19	163 8/19	41 8/19	150 8/19	81 8/19	125 8/19	133 8/19	240 8/19	-61 11/19	2022
272 8/19	-25 11/19	111 8/19	200 8/19	-1 11/19	206 8/19	15 8/19	96 8/19	170 8/19	28 8/19	176 8/19	60 8/19	126 8/19	140 8/19	43 8/19	146 8/19	75 8/19	238 8/19	-59 11/19	2022
-55 11/19	234 8/19	208 8/19	11 8/19	105 8/19	201 8/19	5 8/19	178 8/19	56 8/19	90 8/19	171 8/19	35 8/19	148 8/19	71 8/19	120 8/19	141 8/19	50 8/19	-21 11/19	268 8/19	2022
-53 11/19	232 8/19	195 8/19	6 8/19	215 8/19	13 8/19	101 8/19	165 8/19	36 8/19	185 8/19	58 8/19	86 8/19	135 8/19	51 8/19	155 8/19	73 8/19	116 8/19	-19 11/19	266 8/19	2022
-51 11/19	230 8/19	20 8/19	103 8/19	191 8/19	8/19	216 8/19	65 8/19	88 8/19	161 8/19	30 8/19	186 8/19	80 8/19	118 8/19	131 8/19	45 8/19	156 8/19	-17 11/19	264 8/19	2022
-49 11/19	228 8/19	-2 11/19	212 8/19	19 8/19	108 8/19	194 8/19	27 8/19	182 8/19	64 8/19	93 8/19	164 8/19	42 8/19	152 8/19	79 8/19	123 8/19	134 8/19	-15 11/19	262 8/19	2022
-47 11/19	226 8/19	109 8/19	198 8/19	-11/19	207 8/19	17 8/19	94 8/19	168 8/19	29 8/19	177 8/19	62 8/19	124 8/19	138 8/19	44 8/19	147 8/19	77 8/19	-13 11/19	260 8/19	2022
-45 11/19	224 8/19	209 8/19	12 8/19	107 8/19	199 8/19	3 8/19	179 8/19	57 8/19	92 8/19	169 8/19	33 8/19	149 8/19	72 8/19	122 8/19	139 8/19	48 8/19	-11 11/19	258 8/19	2022
-43 11/19	222 8/19	197 8/19	4 8/19	213 8/19	14 8/19	102 8/19	167 8/19	34 8/19	183 8/19	59 8/19	87 8/19	137 8/19	49 8/19	153 8/19	74 8/19	117 8/19	-9 11/19	256 8/19	2022
-41 11/19	220 8/19	18 8/19	104 8/19	192 8/19	2 8/19	214 8/19	63 8/19	89 8/19	162 8/19	32 8/19	184 8/19	78 8/19	119 8/19	132 8/19	47 8/19	154 8/19	-7 11/19	254 8/19	2022
-39 11/19	233 8/19	-36 11/19	-34 11/19	-32 11/19	-30 11/19	-28 11/19	-26 11/19	-24 11/19	-23 11/19	231 8/19	229 8/19	227 8/19	225 8/19	223 8/19	221 8/19	219 8/19	235 8/19	252 8/19	2022
269 8/19	251 8/19	253 8/19	255 8/19	257 8/19	259 8/19	261 8/19	263 8/19	265 8/19	-57 11/19	-58 11/19	-60 11/19	-62 11/19	-64 11/19	-66 11/19	-68 11/19	-70 11/19	-72 11/19	267 8/19	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal sums resulting in a **pan-diagonal** magic square of order 15. The magic sums are $S_{19 \times 19} := 2022$, $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{34374}{19}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{30330}{19}$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{10110}{19}$.

2.13 Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 20

In this case, we shall write four types of **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic square of order 20 with magic sums 2022.

2.13.1 Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 4

A **block-wise** magic square of order 20 with blocks of order 4 and magic sum 2022 is given by

pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	90,6	101,6	-79,4	291,6	67,6	124,6	-62,4	274,6	49,6	142,6	-40,4	252,6	26,6	165,6	-23,4	235,6	8,6	183,6	-1,4	213,6	2022
2022	-88,4	300,6	81,6	110,6	-65,4	277,6	64,6	127,6	-47,4	259,6	42,6	149,6	-24,4	236,6	25,6	166,6	-6,4	218,6	3,6	188,6	2022
2022	281,6	-89,4	111,6	100,6	264,6	-72,4	134,6	77,6	242,6	-50,4	152,6	59,6	225,6	-33,4	175,6	36,6	203,6	-11,4	193,6	18,6	2022
2022	120,6	91,6	290,6	-98,4	137,6	74,6	267,6	-75,4	159,6	52,6	249,6	-57,4	176,6	35,6	226,6	-34,4	198,6	13,6	208,6	-16,4	2022
2022	29,6	162,6	-20,4	232,6	6,6	185,6	-3,4	215,6	88,6	103,6	-81,4	293,6	70,6	121,6	-59,4	271,6	47,6	144,6	-42,4	254,6	2022
2022	-27,4	239,6	22,6	169,6	-4,4	216,6	5,6	186,6	-86,4	298,6	83,6	108,6	-68,4	280,6	61,6	130,6	-45,4	257,6	44,6	147,6	2022
2022	222,6	-30,4	172,6	39,6	205,6	-13,4	195,6	16,6	283,6	-91,4	113,6	98,6	261,6	-69,4	131,6	80,6	244,6	-52,4	154,6	57,6	2022
2022	179,6	32,6	229,6	-37,4	196,6	15,6	206,6	-14,4	118,6	93,6	288,6	-96,4	140,6	71,6	270,6	-78,4	157,6	54,6	247,6	-55,4	2022
2022	68,6	123,6	-61,4	273,6	50,6	141,6	-39,4	251,6	27,6	164,6	-22,4	234,6	9,6	182,6	-0,4	212,6	86,6	105,6	-83,4	295,6	2022
2022	-66,4	278,6	63,6	128,6	-48,4	260,6	41,6	150,6	-25,4	237,6	24,6	167,6	-7,4	219,6	2,6	189,6	-84,4	296,6	85,6	106,6	2022
2022	263,6	-71,4	133,6	78,6	241,6	-49,4	151,6	60,6	224,6	-32,4	174,6	37,6	202,6	-10,4	192,6	19,6	285,6	-93,4	115,6	96,6	2022
2022	138,6	73,6	268,6	-76,4	160,6	51,6	250,6	-58,4	177,6	34,6	227,6	-35,4	199,6	12,6	209,6	-17,4	116,6	95,6	286,6	-94,4	2022
2022	7,6	184,6	-2,4	214,6	89,6	102,6	-80,4	292,6	66,6	125,6	-63,4	275,6	48,6	143,6	-41,4	253,6	30,6	161,6	-19,4	231,6	2022
2022	-5,4	217,6	4,6	187,6	-87,4	299,6	82,6	109,6	-64,4	276,6	65,6	126,6	-46,4	258,6	43,6	148,6	-28,4	240,6	21,6	170,6	2022
2022	204,6	-12,4	194,6	17,6	282,6	-90,4	112,6	99,6	265,6	-73,4	135,6	76,6	243,6	-51,4	153,6	58,6	221,6	-29,4	171,6	40,6	2022
2022	197,6	14,6	207,6	-15,4	119,6	92,6	289,6	-97,4	136,6	75,6	266,6	-74,4	158,6	53,6	248,6	-56,4	180,6	31,6	230,6	-38,4	2022
2022	46,6	145,6	-43,4	255,6	28,6	163,6	-21,4	233,6	10,6	181,6	0,6	211,6	87,6	104,6	-82,4	294,6	69,6	122,6	-60,4	272,6	2022
2022	-44,4	256,6	45,6	146,6	-26,4	238,6	23,6	168,6	-8,4	220,6	1,6	190,6	-85,4	297,6	84,6	107,6	-67,4	279,6	62,6	129,6	2022
2022	245,6	-53,4	155,6	56,6	223,6	-31,4	173,6	38,6	201,6	-9,4	191,6	20,6	284,6	-92,4	114,6	97,6	262,6	-70,4	132,6	79,6	2022
2022	156,6	55,6	246,6	-54,4	178,6	33,6	228,6	-36,4	200,6	11,6	210,6	-18,4	117,6	94,6	287,6	-95,4	139,6	72,6	269,6	-77,4	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 20. The magic sums are $S_{20 \times 20} := 2022$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{2022}{5}$.

2.13.2 Block-Wise With Blocks of Order 5

A **block-wise** magic square of order 20 with blocks of order 4 and magic sum 2022 is given by

pan	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022
2022	-92,4	35,6	83,6	211,6	259,6	-87,4	40,6	88,6	216,6	264,6	-98,4	29,6	77,6	205,6	253,6	-85,4	42,6	90,6	218,6	266,6	2022
2022	163,6	291,6	-60,4	-12,4	115,6	168,6	296,6	-55,4	-7,4	120,6	157,6	285,6	-66,4	-18,4	109,6	170,6	298,6	-53,4	-5,4	122,6	2022
2022	19,6	67,6	195,6	243,6	-28,4	24,6	72,6	200,6	248,6	-23,4	13,6	61,6	189,6	237,6	-34,4	26,6	74,6	202,6	250,6	-21,4	2022
2022	275,6	-76,4	51,6	99,6	147,6	280,6	-71,4	56,6	104,6	152,6	269,6	-82,4	45,6	93,6	141,6	282,6	-69,4	58,6	106,6	154,6	2022
2022	131,6	179,6	227,6	-44,4	3,6	136,6	184,6	232,6	-39,4	8,6	125,6	173,6	221,6	-50,4	-2,4	138,6	186,6	234,6	-37,4	10,6	2022
2022	-97,4	30,6	78,6	206,6	254,6	-86,4	41,6	89,6	217,6	265,6	-91,4	36,6	84,6	212,6	260,6	-88,4	39,6	87,6	215,6	263,6	2022
2022	158,6	286,6	-65,4	-17,4	110,6	169,6	297,6	-54,4	-6,4	121,6	164,6	292,6	-59,4	-11,4	116,6	167,6	295,6	-56,4	-8,4	119,6	2022
2022	14,6	62,6	190,6	238,6	-33,4	25,6	73,6	201,6	249,6	-22,4	20,6	68,6	196,6	244,6	-27,4	23,6	71,6	199,6	247,6	-24,4	2022
2022	270,6	-81,4	46,6	94,6	142,6	281,6	-70,4	57,6	105,6	153,6	276,6	-75,4	52,6	100,6	148,6	279,6	-72,4	55,6	103,6	151,6	2022
2022	126,6	174,6	222,6	-49,4	-1,4	137,6	185,6	233,6	-38,4	9,6	132,6	180,6	228,6	-43,4	4,6	135,6	183,6	231,6	-40,4	7,6	2022
2022	-83,4	44,6	92,6	220,6	268,6	-96,4	31,6	79,6	207,6	255,6	-89,4	38,6	86,6	214,6	262,6	-94,4	33,6	81,6	209,6	257,6	2022
2022	172,6	300,6	-51,4	-3,4	124,6	159,6	287,6	-64,4	-16,4	111,6	166,6	294,6	-57,4	-9,4	118,6	161,6	289,6	-62,4	-14,4	113,6	2022
2022	28,6	76,6	204,6	252,6	-19,4	15,6	63,6	191,6	239,6	-32,4	22,6	70,6	198,6	246,6	-25,4	17,6	65,6	193,6	241,6	-30,4	2022
2022	284,6	-67,4	60,6	108,6	156,6	271,6	-80,4	47,6	95,6	143,6	278,6	-73,4	54,6	102,6	150,6	273,6	-78,4	49,6	97,6	145,6	2022
2022	140,6	188,6	236,6	-35,4	12,6	127,6	175,6	223,6	-48,4	-0,4	134,6	182,6	230,6	-41,4	6,6	129,6	177,6	225,6	-46,4	1,6	2022
2022	-90,4	37,6	85,6	213,6	261,6	-93,4	34,6	82,6	210,6	258,6	-84,4	43,6	91,6	219,6	267,6	-95,4	32,6	80,6	208,6	256,6	2022
2022	165,6	293,6	-58,4	-10,4	117,6	162,6	290,6	-61,4	-13,4	114,6	171,6	299,6	-52,4	-4,4	123,6	160,6	288,6	-63,4	-15,4	112,6	2022
2022	21,6	69,6	197,6	245,6	-26,4	18,6	66,6	194,6	242,6	-29,4	27,6	75,6	203,6	251,6	-20,4	16,6	64,6	192,6	240,6	-31,4	2022
2022	277,6	-74,4	53,6	101,6	149,6	274,6	-77,4	50,6	98,6	146,6	283,6	-68,4	59,6	107,6	155,6	272,6	-79,4	48,6	96,6	144,6	2022
	133,6	181,6	229,6	-42,4	5,6	130,6	178,6	226,6	-45,4	2,6	139,6	187,6	235,6	-36,4	11,6	128,6	176,6	224,6	-47,4	0,6	2022
	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic square of different magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 20.

2.13.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 20 with blocks of order 10 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																				2022
291,6	286,6	-83,4	284,6	-81,4	-85,4	-95,4	298,6	-97,4	292,6	273,6	268,6	-65,4	266,6	-63,4	-67,4	-77,4	280,6	-79,4	274,6	2022
-86,4	69,6	164,6	-26,4	196,6	70,6	163,6	-25,4	195,6	288,6	-68,4	73,6	160,6	-22,4	192,6	74,6	159,6	-21,4	191,6	270,6	2022
289,6	4,6	165,6	100,6	133,6	3,6	166,6	99,6	134,6	-87,4	271,6	0,6	169,6	96,6	137,6	-0,4	170,6	95,6	138,6	-69,4	2022
-88,4	228,6	5,6	132,6	37,6	227,6	6,6	131,6	38,6	290,6	-70,4	224,6	9,6	128,6	41,6	223,6	10,6	127,6	42,6	272,6	2022
296,6	101,6	68,6	197,6	36,6	102,6	67,6	198,6	35,6	-94,4	278,6	105,6	64,6	201,6	32,6	106,6	63,6	202,6	31,6	-76,4	2022
-98,4	71,6	162,6	-24,4	194,6	72,6	161,6	-23,4	193,6	300,6	-80,4	75,6	158,6	-20,4	190,6	76,6	157,6	-19,4	189,6	282,6	2022
293,6	2,6	167,6	98,6	135,6	1,6	168,6	97,6	136,6	-91,4	275,6	-1,4	171,6	94,6	139,6	-2,4	172,6	93,6	140,6	-73,4	2022
-92,4	226,6	7,6	130,6	39,6	225,6	8,6	129,6	40,6	294,6	-74,4	222,6	11,6	126,6	43,6	221,6	12,6	125,6	44,6	276,6	2022
295,6	103,6	66,6	199,6	34,6	104,6	65,6	200,6	33,6	-93,4	277,6	107,6	62,6	203,6	30,6	108,6	61,6	204,6	29,6	-75,4	2022
-90,4	-84,4	285,6	-82,4	283,6	287,6	297,6	-96,4	299,6	-89,4	-72,4	-66,4	267,6	-64,4	265,6	269,6	279,6	-78,4	281,6	-71,4	2022
255,6	250,6	-47,4	248,6	-45,4	-49,4	-59,4	262,6	-61,4	256,6	237,6	232,6	-29,4	230,6	-27,4	-31,4	-41,4	244,6	-43,4	238,6	2022
-50,4	77,6	156,6	-18,4	188,6	78,6	155,6	-17,4	187,6	252,6	-32,4	81,6	152,6	-14,4	184,6	82,6	151,6	-13,4	183,6	234,6	2022
253,6	-3,4	173,6	92,6	141,6	-4,4	174,6	91,6	142,6	-51,4	235,6	-7,4	177,6	88,6	145,6	-8,4	178,6	87,6	146,6	-33,4	2022
-52,4	220,6	13,6	124,6	45,6	219,6	14,6	123,6	46,6	254,6	-34,4	216,6	17,6	120,6	49,6	215,6	18,6	119,6	50,6	236,6	2022
260,6	109,6	60,6	205,6	28,6	110,6	59,6	206,6	27,6	-58,4	242,6	113,6	56,6	209,6	24,6	114,6	55,6	210,6	23,6	-40,4	2022
-62,4	79,6	154,6	-16,4	186,6	80,6	153,6	-15,4	185,6	264,6	-44,4	83,6	150,6	-12,4	182,6	84,6	149,6	-11,4	181,6	246,6	2022
257,6	-5,4	175,6	90,6	143,6	-6,4	176,6	89,6	144,6	-55,4	239,6	-9,4	179,6	86,6	147,6	-10,4	180,6	85,6	148,6	-37,4	2022
-56,4	218,6	15,6	122,6	47,6	217,6	16,6	121,6	48,6	258,6	-38,4	214,6	19,6	118,6	51,6	213,6	20,6	117,6	52,6	240,6	2022
259,6	111,6	58,6	207,6	26,6	112,6	57,6	208,6	25,6	-57,4	241,6	115,6	54,6	211,6	22,6	116,6	53,6	212,6	21,6	-39,4	2022
-54,4	-48,4	249,6	-46,4	247,6	251,6	261,6	-60,4	263,6	-53,4	-36,4	-30,4	231,6	-28,4	229,6	233,6	243,6	-42,4	245,6	-35,4	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 10 are magic square of equal magic sums resulting in a magic square of order 20. The magic sums are $S_{20 \times 20} := 2022$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1011$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{2022}{5}$.

2.13.4 Bordered Magic Squares Of Order 10

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 20 with bordered magic squares of order 10 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																				2022	
292	287	-83	285	-81	-85	-95	299	-97	293	242	237	-33	235	-31	-35	-45	249	-47	243	2022	
-86	-73,4	-79,4	281	283	270	-68,4	272	-74,4	289	-36	-23,4	-29,4	231	233	220	-18,4	222	-24,4	239	2022	
290	-76,4	265	263	-64,4	269	-63,4	-61,4	279	-87	240	-26,4	215	213	-14,4	219	-13,4	-11,4	229	-37	2022	
-88	-75,4	-65,4	-50,4	255	-56,4	257	268	278	291	-38	-25,4	-15,4	-0,4	205	-6,4	207	218	228	241	2022	
297	-70,4	-59,4	-55,4	256	-49,4	254	262	273	-94	247	-20,4	-9,4	-5,4	206	0,6	204	212	223	-44	2022	
-98	280	-57,4	259	-54,4	253	-52,4	260	-77,4	301	-48	230	-7,4	209	-4,4	203	-2,4	210	-27,4	251	2022	
294	275	261	252	-51,4	258	-53,4	-58,4	-72,4	-91	244	225	211	202	-1,4	208	-3,4	-8,4	-22,4	-41	2022	
-92	274	264	-60,4	267	-66,4	266	-62,4	-71,4	295	-42	224	214	-10,4	217	-16,4	216	-12,4	-21,4	245	2022	
296	277	282	-78,4	-80,4	-67,4	271	-69,4	276	-93	246	227	232	-28,4	-30,4	-17,4	221	-19,4	226	-43	2022	
-90	-84	286	-82	284	288	298	-96	300	-89	-40	-34	236	-32	234	238	248	-46	250	-39	2022	
142	137	67	135	69	65	55	149	53	143	192	187	17	185	19	15	5	199	3	193	2022	
64	76,6	70,6	131	133	120	81,6	122	75,6	139	14	26,6	20,6	181	183	170	31,6	172	25,6	189	2022	
140	73,6	115	113	85,6	119	86,6	88,6	129	63	190	23,6	165	163	35,6	169	36,6	38,6	179	13	2022	
62	74,6	84,6	99,6	105	93,6	107	118	128	141	12	24,6	34,6	49,6	155	43,6	157	168	178	191	2022	
147	79,6	90,6	94,6	106	101	104	112	123	56	197	29,6	40,6	44,6	156	50,6	154	162	173	6	2022	
52	130	92,6	109	95,6	103	97,6	110	72,6	151	2	180	42,6	159	45,6	153	47,6	160	22,6	201	2022	
144	125	111	102	98,6	108	96,6	91,6	77,6	59	194	175	161	152	48,6	158	46,6	41,6	27,6	9	2022	
58	124	114	89,6	117	83,6	116	87,6	78,6	145	8	174	164	39,6	167	33,6	166	37,6	28,6	195	2022	
146	127	132	71,6	69,6	82,6	121	80,6	126	57	196	177	182	21,6	19,6	32,6	171	30,6	176	7	2022	
60	66	136	68	134	138	148	54	150	61	10	16	186	18	184	188	198	4	200	11	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 10 are magic square of equal magic sums resulting in a magic square of order 20. The magic sums are $S_{20 \times 20} := 2022$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1011$, $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4044}{5}$, $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3033}{5}$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{2022}{5}$.

2.14 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 21

In this case, we shall write **block-wise** magic square of order 21 with blocks of orders 3 and 7, and magic sum 2022.

2.14.1 Blocks of Order 3

A **block-wise** magic square of order 21 with block of order 3 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																					2022	
121 2/7	-13 5/7	181 2/7	149 2/7	250 2/7	-110 5/7	62 2/7	-35 5/7	262 2/7	87 2/7	294 2/7	-92 5/7	43 2/7	-57 5/7	303 2/7	130 2/7	228 2/7	-69 5/7	80 2/7	8 2/7	200 2/7	2022	
175 2/7	118 2/7	-4 5/7	-106 5/7	162 2/7	233 2/7	258 2/7	52 2/7	-21 5/7	-83 5/7	96 2/7	276 2/7	299 2/7	30 2/7	-40 5/7	-65 5/7	140 2/7	214 2/7	197 2/7	74 2/7	17 2/7	2022	
-7 5/7	184 2/7	112 2/7	246 2/7	-123 5/7	166 2/7	-31 5/7	272 2/7	48 2/7	285 2/7	-101 5/7	105 2/7	-53 5/7	316 2/7	26 2/7	224 2/7	-79 5/7	144 2/7	11 2/7	206 2/7	71 2/7	2022	
148 2/7	215 2/7	-74 5/7	67 2/7	18 2/7	203 2/7	122 2/7	-12 5/7	179 2/7	163 2/7	238 2/7	-112 5/7	44 2/7	-22 5/7	267 2/7	104 2/7	279 2/7	-94 5/7	24 2/7	-41 5/7	306 2/7	2022	
-78 5/7	135 2/7	232 2/7	207 2/7	77 2/7	4 2/7	176 2/7	116 2/7	-3 5/7	-118 5/7	160 2/7	247 2/7	271 2/7	57 2/7	-39 5/7	-98 5/7	94 2/7	293 2/7	315 2/7	33 2/7	-59 5/7	2022	
219 2/7	-61 5/7	131 2/7	14 2/7	193 2/7	81 2/7	-9 5/7	185 2/7	113 2/7	244 2/7	-109 5/7	154 2/7	-26 5/7	254 2/7	61 2/7	283 2/7	-84 5/7	90 2/7	-50 5/7	297 2/7	42 2/7	2022	
86 2/7	292 2/7	-89 5/7	41 2/7	-56 5/7	304 2/7	129 2/7	231 2/7	-71 5/7	85 2/7	5 2/7	198 2/7	109 2/7	-2 5/7	182 2/7	164 2/7	239 2/7	-114 5/7	58 2/7	-34 5/7	265 2/7	2022	
-85 5/7	99 2/7	275 2/7	300 2/7	31 2/7	-42 5/7	-62 5/7	138 2/7	213 2/7	194 2/7	72 2/7	22 2/7	186 2/7	119 2/7	-16 5/7	-117 5/7	158 2/7	248 2/7	259 2/7	55 2/7	-25 5/7	2022	
288 2/7	-102 5/7	103 2/7	-52 5/7	314 2/7	27 2/7	222 2/7	-80 5/7	147 2/7	9 2/7	211 2/7	68 2/7	-6 5/7	172 2/7	123 2/7	242 2/7	-108 5/7	155 2/7	-28 5/7	268 2/7	49 2/7	2022	
151 2/7	249 2/7	-111 5/7	59 2/7	-33 5/7	263 2/7	100 2/7	280 2/7	-91 5/7	23 2/7	-43 5/7	309 2/7	146 2/7	216 2/7	-73 5/7	66 2/7	21 2/7	201 2/7	127 2/7	-15 5/7	177 2/7	2022	
-107 5/7	161 2/7	235 2/7	260 2/7	53 2/7	-24 5/7	-97 5/7	97 2/7	289 2/7	313 2/7	36 2/7	-60 5/7	-77 5/7	136 2/7	230 2/7	210 2/7	75 2/7	3 2/7	173 2/7	114 2/7	1 2/7	2022	
245 2/7	-121 5/7	165 2/7	-30 5/7	269 2/7	50 2/7	286 2/7	-88 5/7	91 2/7	-47 5/7	296 2/7	40 2/7	220 2/7	-63 5/7	132 2/7	12 2/7	192 2/7	84 2/7	-11 5/7	190 2/7	110 2/7	2022	
83 2/7	6 2/7	199 2/7	108 2/7	2/7	180 2/7	169 2/7	236 2/7	-116 5/7	46 2/7	-23 5/7	266 2/7	101 2/7	281 2/7	-93 5/7	37 2/7	-55 5/7	307 2/7	128 2/7	229 2/7	-68 5/7	2022	
195 2/7	73 2/7	20 2/7	189 2/7	117 2/7	-17 5/7	-120 5/7	156 2/7	253 2/7	270 2/7	56 2/7	-37 5/7	-96 5/7	95 2/7	290 2/7	301 2/7	34 2/7	-46 5/7	-64 5/7	141 2/7	212 2/7	2022	
10 2/7	209 2/7	69 2/7	-8 5/7	171 2/7	126 2/7	240 2/7	-103 5/7	152 2/7	-27 5/7	256 2/7	60 2/7	284 2/7	-87 5/7	92 2/7	-49 5/7	310 2/7	28 2/7	225 2/7	-81 5/7	145 2/7	2022	
38 2/7	-54 5/7	305 2/7	142 2/7	217 2/7	-70 5/7	65 2/7	19 2/7	204 2/7	125 2/7	-14 5/7	178 2/7	150 2/7	252 2/7	-113 5/7	64 2/7	-36 5/7	261 2/7	88 2/7	291 2/7	-90 5/7	2022	
302 2/7	32 2/7	-45 5/7	-76 5/7	139 2/7	226 2/7	208 2/7	78 2/7	2 2/7	174 2/7	115 2/7	- 5/7	-104 5/7	159 2/7	234 2/7	257 2/7	51 2/7	-19 5/7	-86 5/7	98 2/7	277 2/7	2022	
-51 5/7	311 2/7	29 2/7	223 2/7	-67 5/7	133 2/7	15 2/7	191 2/7	82 2/7	-10 5/7	188 2/7	111 2/7	243 2/7	-122 5/7	168 2/7	-32 5/7	274 2/7	47 2/7	287 2/7	-100 5/7	102 2/7	2022	
45 2/7	-20 5/7	264 2/7	106 2/7	278 2/7	-95 5/7	25 2/7	-44 5/7	308 2/7	143 2/7	218 2/7	-72 5/7	79 2/7	7 2/7	202 2/7	107 2/7	-1 5/7	183 2/7	167 2/7	237 2/7	-115 5/7	2022	
273 2/7	54 2/7	-38 5/7	-99 5/7	93 2/7	295 2/7	312 2/7	35 2/7	-58 5/7	-75 5/7	137 2/7	227 2/7	196 2/7	76 2/7	16 2/7	187 2/7	120 2/7	-18 5/7	-119 5/7	157 2/7	251 2/7	2022	
-29 5/7	255 2/7	63 2/7	282 2/7	-82 5/7	89 2/7	-48 5/7	298 2/7	39 2/7	221 2/7	-66 5/7	134 2/7	13 2/7	205 2/7	70 2/7	-5 5/7	170 2/7	124 2/7	241 2/7	-105 5/7	153 2/7	2022	
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 3 are of **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 21. The magic sums are $S_{21 \times 21} := 2022$, $S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := \frac{2022}{7}$

2.14.2 Blocks of Order 7

A **block-wise** magic square of order 21 with block of order 7 and magic sum 2022 is given by

																					2022
-123 5/7	-13 5/7	30 2/7	118 2/7	140 2/7	250 2/7	272 2/7	-121 5/7	-14 5/7	29 2/7	117 2/7	141 2/7	249 2/7	273 2/7	-122 5/7	-15 5/7	31 2/7	116 2/7	142 2/7	248 2/7	274 2/7	2022
245 2/7	271 2/7	-105 5/7	-18 5/7	28 2/7	114 2/7	139 2/7	246 2/7	270 2/7	-104 5/7	-16 5/7	27 2/7	113 2/7	138 2/7	247 2/7	269 2/7	-103 5/7	-17 5/7	26 2/7	115 2/7	137 2/7	2022
112 2/7	135 2/7	244 2/7	266 2/7	-106 5/7	-5 5/7	23 2/7	111 2/7	134 2/7	243 2/7	267 2/7	-107 5/7	2 2/7	25 2/7	110 2/7	136 2/7	242 2/7	268 2/7	-108 5/7	1 2/7	24 2/7	2022
-1 5/7	41 2/7	107 2/7	133 2/7	240 2/7	265 2/7	-111 5/7	-2 5/7	42 2/7	109 2/7	132 2/7	239 2/7	264 2/7	-110 5/7	-3 5/7	43 2/7	108 2/7	131 2/7	241 2/7	263 2/7	-109 5/7	2022
261 2/7	-112 5/7	-6 5/7	40 2/7	125 2/7	128 2/7	238 2/7	260 2/7	-113 5/7	-5 5/7	39 2/7	126 2/7	130 2/7	237 2/7	262 2/7	-114 5/7	-4 5/7	38 2/7	127 2/7	129 2/7	236 2/7	2022
146 2/7	233 2/7	259 2/7	-116 5/7	-7 5/7	35 2/7	124 2/7	147 2/7	235 2/7	258 2/7	-117 5/7	-8 5/7	36 2/7	123 2/7	148 2/7	234 2/7	257 2/7	-115 5/7	-9 5/7	37 2/7	122 2/7	2022
34 2/7	119 2/7	145 2/7	251 2/7	254 2/7	-118 5/7	-11 5/7	33 2/7	120 2/7	144 2/7	252 2/7	256 2/7	-119 5/7	-12 5/7	32 2/7	121 2/7	143 2/7	253 2/7	255 2/7	-120 5/7	-10 5/7	2022
-81 5/7	-34 5/7	9 2/7	97 2/7	161 2/7	229 2/7	293 2/7	-79 5/7	-35 5/7	8 2/7	96 2/7	162 2/7	228 2/7	294 2/7	-80 5/7	-36 5/7	10 2/7	95 2/7	163 2/7	227 2/7	295 2/7	2022
224 2/7	292 2/7	-63 5/7	-39 5/7	7 2/7	93 2/7	160 2/7	225 2/7	291 2/7	-62 5/7	-37 5/7	6 2/7	92 2/7	159 2/7	226 2/7	290 2/7	-61 5/7	-38 5/7	5 2/7	94 2/7	158 2/7	2022
91 2/7	156 2/7	223 2/7	287 2/7	-64 5/7	-21 5/7	2 2/7	90 2/7	155 2/7	222 2/7	288 2/7	-65 5/7	-20 5/7	4 2/7	89 2/7	157 2/7	221 2/7	289 2/7	-66 5/7	-19 5/7	3 2/7	2022
-22 5/7	20 2/7	86 2/7	154 2/7	219 2/7	286 2/7	-69 5/7	-23 5/7	21 2/7	88 2/7	153 2/7	218 2/7	285 2/7	-68 5/7	-24 5/7	22 2/7	87 2/7	152 2/7	220 2/7	284 2/7	-67 5/7	2022
282 2/7	-70 5/7	-27 5/7	19 2/7	104 2/7	149 2/7	217 2/7	281 2/7	-71 5/7	-26 5/7	18 2/7	105 2/7	151 2/7	216 2/7	283 2/7	-72 5/7	-25 5/7	17 2/7	106 2/7	150 2/7	215 2/7	2022
167 2/7	212 2/7	280 2/7	-74 5/7	-28 5/7	14 2/7	103 2/7	168 2/7	214 2/7	279 2/7	-75 5/7	-29 5/7	15 2/7	102 2/7	169 2/7	213 2/7	278 2/7	-73 5/7	-30 5/7	16 2/7	101 2/7	2022
13 2/7	98 2/7	166 2/7	230 2/7	275 2/7	-76 5/7	-32 5/7	12 2/7	99 2/7	165 2/7	231 2/7	277 2/7	-77 5/7	-33 5/7	11 2/7	100 2/7	164 2/7	232 2/7	276 2/7	-78 5/7	-31 5/7	2022
-102 5/7	-55 5/7	51 2/7	76 2/7	182 2/7	208 2/7	314 2/7	-100 5/7	-56 5/7	50 2/7	75 2/7	183 2/7	207 2/7	315 2/7	-101 5/7	-57 5/7	52 2/7	74 2/7	184 2/7	206 2/7	316 2/7	2022
203 2/7	313 2/7	-84 5/7	-60 5/7	49 2/7	72 2/7	181 2/7	204 2/7	312 2/7	-83 5/7	-58 5/7	48 2/7	71 2/7	180 2/7	205 2/7	311 2/7	-82 5/7	-59 5/7	47 2/7	73 2/7	179 2/7	2022
70 2/7	177 2/7	202 2/7	308 2/7	-85 5/7	-42 5/7	44 2/7	69 2/7	176 2/7	201 2/7	309 2/7	-86 5/7	-41 5/7	46 2/7	68 2/7	178 2/7	200 2/7	310 2/7	-87 5/7	-40 5/7	45 2/7	2022
-43 5/7	62 2/7	65 2/7	175 2/7	198 2/7	307 2/7	-90 5/7	-44 5/7	63 2/7	67 2/7	174 2/7	197 2/7	306 2/7	-89 5/7	-45 5/7	64 2/7	66 2/7	173 2/7	199 2/7	305 2/7	-88 5/7	2022
303 2/7	-91 5/7	-48 5/7	61 2/7	83 2/7	170 2/7	196 2/7	302 2/7	-92 5/7	-47 5/7	60 2/7	84 2/7	172 2/7	195 2/7	304 2/7	-93 5/7	-46 5/7	59 2/7	85 2/7	171 2/7	194 2/7	2022
188 2/7	191 2/7	301 2/7	-95 5/7	-49 5/7	56 2/7	82 2/7	189 2/7	193 2/7	300 2/7	-96 5/7	-50 5/7	57 2/7	81 2/7	190 2/7	192 2/7	299 2/7	-94 5/7	-51 5/7	58 2/7	80 2/7	2022
55 2/7	77 2/7	187 2/7	209 2/7	296 2/7	-97 5/7	-53 5/7	54 2/7	78 2/7	186 2/7	210 2/7	298 2/7	-98 5/7	-54 5/7	53 2/7	79 2/7	185 2/7	211 2/7	297 2/7	-99 5/7	-52 5/7	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 21. The magic sums are $S_{21 \times 21} := 2022$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := 674$.

2.15 Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 22

In this case, we shall write **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 with blocks of orders 4 and 5, and magic sum 2022.

2.15.1 Blocks of Order 4

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

2022

-129 13/22	322 9/22	-137 13/22	320 9/22	-135 13/22	318 9/22	-133 13/22	316 9/22	-131 13/22	314 9/22	-149 13/22	323 9/22	-127 13/22	310 9/22	-125 13/22	308 9/22	-123 13/22	306 9/22	-121 13/22	304 9/22	-119 13/22	312 9/22	2022
-117 13/22	81 9/22	92 9/22	-88 13/22	282 9/22	58 9/22	115 9/22	-71 13/22	265 9/22	40 9/22	133 9/22	-49 13/22	243 9/22	17 9/22	156 9/22	-32 13/22	226 9/22	-13/22	174 9/22	-10 13/22	204 9/22	301 9/22	2022
300 9/22	-97 13/22	291 9/22	72 9/22	101 9/22	-74 13/22	268 9/22	55 9/22	118 9/22	-56 13/22	250 9/22	33 9/22	140 9/22	-33 13/22	227 9/22	16 9/22	157 9/22	-15 13/22	209 9/22	-5 13/22	179 9/22	-116 13/22	2022
-115 13/22	272 9/22	-98 13/22	102 9/22	91 9/22	255 9/22	-81 13/22	125 9/22	68 9/22	233 9/22	-59 13/22	143 9/22	50 9/22	216 9/22	-42 13/22	166 9/22	27 9/22	194 9/22	-20 13/22	184 9/22	9 9/22	299 9/22	2022
298 9/22	111 9/22	82 9/22	281 9/22	-107 13/22	128 9/22	65 9/22	258 9/22	-84 13/22	150 9/22	43 9/22	240 9/22	-66 13/22	167 9/22	26 9/22	217 9/22	-43 13/22	189 9/22	4 9/22	199 9/22	-25 13/22	-114 13/22	2022
-113 13/22	20 9/22	153 9/22	-29 13/22	223 9/22	-2 13/22	176 9/22	-12 13/22	206 9/22	79 9/22	94 9/22	-90 13/22	284 9/22	61 9/22	112 9/22	-68 13/22	262 9/22	38 9/22	135 9/22	-51 13/22	245 9/22	297 9/22	2022
296 9/22	-36 13/22	230 9/22	13 9/22	160 9/22	-13 13/22	207 9/22	-3 13/22	177 9/22	-95 13/22	289 9/22	74 9/22	99 9/22	-77 13/22	271 9/22	52 9/22	121 9/22	-54 13/22	248 9/22	35 9/22	138 9/22	-112 13/22	2022
-111 13/22	213 9/22	-39 13/22	163 9/22	30 9/22	196 9/22	-22 13/22	186 9/22	7 9/22	274 9/22	-100 13/22	104 9/22	89 9/22	252 9/22	-78 13/22	122 9/22	71 9/22	235 9/22	-61 13/22	145 9/22	48 9/22	295 9/22	2022
294 9/22	170 9/22	23 9/22	220 9/22	-46 13/22	187 9/22	6 9/22	197 9/22	-23 13/22	109 9/22	84 9/22	279 9/22	-105 13/22	131 9/22	62 9/22	261 9/22	-87 13/22	148 9/22	45 9/22	238 9/22	-64 13/22	-110 13/22	2022
-109 13/22	59 9/22	114 9/22	-70 13/22	264 9/22	41 9/22	132 9/22	-48 13/22	242 9/22	18 9/22	155 9/22	-31 13/22	225 9/22	9/22	173 9/22	-9 13/22	203 9/22	77 9/22	96 9/22	-92 13/22	286 9/22	293 9/22	2022
292 9/22	-75 13/22	269 9/22	54 9/22	119 9/22	-57 13/22	251 9/22	32 9/22	141 9/22	-34 13/22	228 9/22	15 9/22	158 9/22	-16 13/22	210 9/22	-6 13/22	180 9/22	-93 13/22	287 9/22	76 9/22	97 9/22	-108 13/22	2022
302 9/22	254 9/22	-80 13/22	124 9/22	69 9/22	232 9/22	-58 13/22	142 9/22	51 9/22	215 9/22	-41 13/22	165 9/22	28 9/22	193 9/22	-19 13/22	183 9/22	10 9/22	276 9/22	-102 13/22	106 9/22	87 9/22	-118 13/22	2022
324 9/22	129 9/22	64 9/22	259 9/22	-85 13/22	151 9/22	42 9/22	241 9/22	-67 13/22	168 9/22	25 9/22	218 9/22	-44 13/22	190 9/22	3 9/22	200 9/22	-26 13/22	107 9/22	86 9/22	277 9/22	-103 13/22	-140 13/22	2022
-141 13/22	-113/22	175 9/22	-11 13/22	205 9/22	80 9/22	93 9/22	-89 13/22	283 9/22	57 9/22	116 9/22	-72 13/22	266 9/22	39 9/22	134 9/22	-50 13/22	244 9/22	21 9/22	152 9/22	-28 13/22	222 9/22	325 9/22	2022
326 9/22	-14 13/22	208 9/22	-4 13/22	178 9/22	-96 13/22	290 9/22	73 9/22	100 9/22	-73 13/22	267 9/22	56 9/22	117 9/22	-55 13/22	249 9/22	34 9/22	139 9/22	-37 13/22	231 9/22	12 9/22	161 9/22	-142 13/22	2022
-143 13/22	195 9/22	-21 13/22	185 9/22	8 9/22	273 9/22	-99 13/22	103 9/22	90 9/22	256 9/22	-82 13/22	126 9/22	67 9/22	234 9/22	-60 13/22	144 9/22	49 9/22	212 9/22	-38 13/22	162 9/22	31 9/22	327 9/22	2022
328 9/22	188 9/22	5 9/22	198 9/22	-24 13/22	110 9/22	83 9/22	280 9/22	-106 13/22	127 9/22	66 9/22	257 9/22	-83 13/22	149 9/22	44 9/22	239 9/22	-65 13/22	171 9/22	22 9/22	221 9/22	-47 13/22	-144 13/22	2022
-145 13/22	37 9/22	136 9/22	-52 13/22	246 9/22	19 9/22	154 9/22	-30 13/22	224 9/22	1 9/22	172 9/22	-8 13/22	202 9/22	78 9/22	95 9/22	-91 13/22	285 9/22	60 9/22	113 9/22	-69 13/22	263 9/22	329 9/22	2022
330 9/22	-53 13/22	247 9/22	36 9/22	137 9/22	-35 13/22	229 9/22	14 9/22	159 9/22	-17 13/22	211 9/22	-7 13/22	181 9/22	-94 13/22	288 9/22	75 9/22	98 9/22	-76 13/22	270 9/22	53 9/22	120 9/22	-146 13/22	2022
-147 13/22	236 9/22	-62 13/22	146 9/22	47 9/22	214 9/22	-40 13/22	164 9/22	29 9/22	192 9/22	-18 13/22	182 9/22	11 9/22	275 9/22	-101 13/22	105 9/22	88 9/22	253 9/22	-79 13/22	123 9/22	70 9/22	331 9/22	2022
332 9/22	147 9/22	46 9/22	237 9/22	-63 13/22	169 9/22	24 9/22	219 9/22	-45 13/22	191 9/22	2 9/22	201 9/22	-27 13/22	108 9/22	85 9/22	278 9/22	-104 13/22	130 9/22	63 9/22	260 9/22	-86 13/22	-148 13/22	2022
-128 13/22	-138 13/22	321 9/22	-136 13/22	319 9/22	-134 13/22	317 9/22	-132 13/22	315 9/22	-130 13/22	333 9/22	-139 13/22	311 9/22	-126 13/22	309 9/22	-124 13/22	307 9/22	-122 13/22	305 9/22	-120 13/22	303 9/22	313 9/22	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic square of equal magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 20. The magic sums are $S_{22 \times 22} := 2022$, $S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{20220}{11}$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4044}{11}$.

2.15.2 Blocks of Order 5

A **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 for the magic sum 2022 is given by

2022

-129 13/22	322 9/22	-137 13/22	320 9/22	-135 13/22	318 9/22	-133 13/22	316 9/22	-131 13/22	314 9/22	-149 13/22	323 9/22	-127 13/22	310 9/22	-125 13/22	308 9/22	-123 13/22	306 9/22	-121 13/22	304 9/22	-119 13/22	312 9/22	2022
-117 13/22	-101 13/22	26 9/22	74 9/22	202 9/22	250 9/22	-96 13/22	31 9/22	79 9/22	207 9/22	255 9/22	-107 13/22	20 9/22	68 9/22	196 9/22	244 9/22	-94 13/22	33 9/22	81 9/22	209 9/22	257 9/22	301 9/22	2022
300 9/22	154 9/22	282 9/22	-69 13/22	-21 13/22	106 9/22	159 9/22	287 9/22	-64 13/22	-16 13/22	111 9/22	148 9/22	276 9/22	-75 13/22	-27 13/22	100 9/22	161 9/22	289 9/22	-62 13/22	-14 13/22	113 9/22	-116 13/22	2022
-115 13/22	10 9/22	58 9/22	186 9/22	234 9/22	-37 13/22	15 9/22	63 9/22	191 9/22	239 9/22	-32 13/22	4 9/22	52 9/22	180 9/22	228 9/22	-43 13/22	17 9/22	65 9/22	193 9/22	241 9/22	-30 13/22	299 9/22	2022
298 9/22	266 9/22	-85 13/22	42 9/22	90 9/22	138 9/22	271 9/22	-80 13/22	47 9/22	95 9/22	143 9/22	260 9/22	-91 13/22	36 9/22	84 9/22	132 9/22	273 9/22	-78 13/22	49 9/22	97 9/22	145 9/22	-114 13/22	2022
-113 13/22	122 9/22	170 9/22	218 9/22	-53 13/22	-5 13/22	127 9/22	175 9/22	223 9/22	-48 13/22	-13/22	116 9/22	164 9/22	212 9/22	-59 13/22	-11 13/22	129 9/22	177 9/22	225 9/22	-46 13/22	1 9/22	297 9/22	2022
296 9/22	-106 13/22	21 9/22	69 9/22	197 9/22	245 9/22	-95 13/22	32 9/22	80 9/22	208 9/22	256 9/22	-100 13/22	27 9/22	75 9/22	203 9/22	251 9/22	-97 13/22	30 9/22	78 9/22	206 9/22	254 9/22	-112 13/22	2022
-111 13/22	149 9/22	277 9/22	-74 13/22	-26 13/22	101 9/22	160 9/22	288 9/22	-63 13/22	-15 13/22	112 9/22	155 9/22	283 9/22	-68 13/22	-20 13/22	107 9/22	158 9/22	286 9/22	-65 13/22	-17 13/22	110 9/22	295 9/22	2022
294 9/22	5 9/22	53 9/22	181 9/22	229 9/22	-42 13/22	16 9/22	64 9/22	192 9/22	240 9/22	-31 13/22	11 9/22	59 9/22	187 9/22	235 9/22	-36 13/22	14 9/22	62 9/22	190 9/22	238 9/22	-33 13/22	-110 13/22	2022
-109 13/22	261 9/22	-90 13/22	37 9/22	85 9/22	133 9/22	272 9/22	-79 13/22	48 9/22	96 9/22	144 9/22	267 9/22	-84 13/22	43 9/22	91 9/22	139 9/22	270 9/22	-81 13/22	46 9/22	94 9/22	142 9/22	293 9/22	2022
292 9/22	117 9/22	165 9/22	213 9/22	-58 13/22	-10 13/22	128 9/22	176 9/22	224 9/22	-47 13/22	9/22	123 9/22	171 9/22	219 9/22	-52 13/22	-4 13/22	126 9/22	174 9/22	222 9/22	-49 13/22	-113/22	-108 13/22	2022
302 9/22	-92 13/22	35 9/22	83 9/22	211 9/22	259 9/22	-105 13/22	22 9/22	70 9/22	198 9/22	246 9/22	-98 13/22	29 9/22	77 9/22	205 9/22	253 9/22	-103 13/22	24 9/22	72 9/22	200 9/22	248 9/22	-118 13/22	2022
324 9/22	163 9/22	291 9/22	-60 13/22	-12 13/22	115 9/22	150 9/22	278 9/22	-73 13/22	-25 13/22	102 9/22	157 9/22	285 9/22	-66 13/22	-18 13/22	109 9/22	152 9/22	280 9/22	-71 13/22	-23 13/22	104 9/22	-140 13/22	2022
-141 13/22	19 9/22	67 9/22	195 9/22	243 9/22	-28 13/22	6 9/22	54 9/22	182 9/22	230 9/22	-41 13/22	13 9/22	61 9/22	189 9/22	237 9/22	-34 13/22	8 9/22	56 9/22	184 9/22	232 9/22	-39 13/22	325 9/22	2022
326 9/22	275 9/22	-76 13/22	51 9/22	99 9/22	147 9/22	262 9/22	-89 13/22	38 9/22	86 9/22	134 9/22	269 9/22	-82 13/22	45 9/22	93 9/22	141 9/22	264 9/22	-87 13/22	40 9/22	88 9/22	136 9/22	-142 13/22	2022
-143 13/22	131 9/22	179 9/22	227 9/22	-44 13/22	3 9/22	118 9/22	166 9/22	214 9/22	-57 13/22	-9 13/22	125 9/22	173 9/22	221 9/22	-50 13/22	-2 13/22	120 9/22	168 9/22	216 9/22	-55 13/22	-7 13/22	327 9/22	2022
328 9/22	-99 13/22	28 9/22	76 9/22	204 9/22	252 9/22	-102 13/22	25 9/22	73 9/22	201 9/22	249 9/22	-93 13/22	34 9/22	82 9/22	210 9/22	258 9/22	-104 13/22	23 9/22	71 9/22	199 9/22	247 9/22	-144 13/22	2022
-145 13/22	156 9/22	284 9/22	-67 13/22	-19 13/22	108 9/22	153 9/22	281 9/22	-70 13/22	-22 13/22	105 9/22	162 9/22	290 9/22	-61 13/22	-13 13/22	114 9/22	151 9/22	279 9/22	-72 13/22	-24 13/22	103 9/22	329 9/22	2022
330 9/22	12 9/22	60 9/22	188 9/22	236 9/22	-35 13/22	9 9/22	57 9/22	185 9/22	233 9/22	-38 13/22	18 9/22	66 9/22	194 9/22	242 9/22	-29 13/22	7 9/22	55 9/22	183 9/22	231 9/22	-40 13/22	-146 13/22	2022
-147 13/22	268 9/22	-83 13/22	44 9/22	92 9/22	140 9/22	265 9/22	-86 13/22	41 9/22	89 9/22	137 9/22	274 9/22	-77 13/22	50 9/22	98 9/22	146 9/22	263 9/22	-88 13/22	39 9/22	87 9/22	135 9/22	331 9/22	2022
332 9/22	124 9/22	172 9/22	220 9/22	-51 13/22	-3 13/22	121 9/22	169 9/22	217 9/22	-54 13/22	-6 13/22	130 9/22	178 9/22	226 9/22	-45 13/22	2 9/22	119 9/22	167 9/22	215 9/22	-56 13/22	-8 13/22	-148 13/22	2022
-128 13/22	-138 13/22	321 9/22	-136 13/22	319 9/22	-134 13/22	317 9/22	-132 13/22	315 9/22	-130 13/22	333 9/22	-139 13/22	311 9/22	-126 13/22	309 9/22	-124 13/22	307 9/22	-122 13/22	305 9/22	-120 13/22	303 9/22	313 9/22	2022
2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022	2022

In this case the blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic square of different magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 20. The magic sums are $S_{22 \times 22} := 2022$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{20220}{11}$.

References

- [1] H. Heinz, Magic Squares, <http://recmath.org/Magic-Squares/magicsquare.htm>
- [2] H. Danielsson, Bordered magic squares, <http://www.magic-squares.info/properties-bordered.html>.
- [3] W. Walkington, Sequenced Concentric Rings on Magic Squares or Magic Tori, <https://carresmagiques.blogspot.com/2019/04/sequenced-concentric-rings-on-magic-squares.html>.
- [4] H. White, Bordered Magic Squares, <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>.

- [5] Inder J. Taneja, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>
- [6] Inder J. Taneja, 2020 In Numbers: Mathematical Style - Revised, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-37, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3596193>
- [7] Inder J. Taneja, 21 Mathematical Highlights for 2021, **Zenodo**, December 26, 2020, pp. 1-75, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4394408>
- [8] Inder J. Taneja, Mathematical Beauty of 2022, **Zenodo**, December 26, 2021, pp. 1-78, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5805264>.
- [9] Inder J. Taneja, Hardy-Ramanujan Number - 1729, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2021, pp. 1-106, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799640>.
- [10] Inder J. Taneja, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations With Fraction Numbers Entries (Version 2), **Zenodo**, August 16, 2021, 1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5209502>.

• Block-Wise

- [11] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [12] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [13] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>
- [14] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [15] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [16] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.

- [17] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [18] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 3 to 31, **Zenodo**, July 19, 2021, pp. 1-181, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5115214>
- [19] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 3 to 47. Zenodo. August 16, 2021, pp. 1-317, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5205214>

• Bordered

- [20] Inder J. Taneja, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>
- [21] Inder J. Taneja, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>
- [22] Inder J. Taneja, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [23] Inder J. Taneja, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>

• Block-Bordered

- [24] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>
- [25] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>
- [26] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>

• Block-Wise and Block-Bordered

- [27] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21 , 21^2 and 2021 . **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>, pp. 1-118.
- [28] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [29] Inder J. Taneja, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples. **Zenodo**. February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>.
- [30] Inder J. Taneja, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>.
- [31] Inder J. Taneja, Minimum Perfect Square Sum Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31. July 20, 2021, pp. 1-82, **Zenodo**. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5116408>.
- [32] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4. **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.
- [33] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of Magic and Bordered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, September 10, pp. 1-99 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500134>.
- [34] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 8, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-80, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514396>.
- [35] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 10, **Zenodo**, September 17, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514398>.
- [36] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12, **Zenodo**, September 23, pp. 1-170, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5523608>
- [37] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 14, **Zenodo**, September 26, pp. 1-198, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528867>
-